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Digital platform and analytic tools for energy

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Table of Contents

Table of Contents	4
List of Figures	6
List of Tables	6
Terms and Abbreviations	7
Executive Summary	9
1. Introduction	10
2. Communication and Dissemination Plan	10
2.1 Main Goal	10
2.2 Objectives	11
2.3 SWOT Analysis	12
2.4 Communication and Dissemination Principles	13
2.5 Internal Rules and Procedures for a proper use of Communication Tools	14
2.6 External Communication	15
2.7 Key Messages	16
3. Communicating the Impact of the PLATOON Project	18
4. Communication Methods and Tools	20
4.1 General Dissemination	21
4.2 Visual Identity	21
4.3 Press Releases	25
4.4 Social Media Strategy	27
4.4.1 Project-specific Twitter Account	29
4.4.2 LinkedIn Company Page	34
4.4.3 Project-specific YouTube Account	36
4.5 Newsletters	36
4.6 Dissemination Campaigns	37
4.7 Industrial Dissemination	38
4.7.1 Conferences, Fairs and Exhibitions	40
4.7.2 Communication and Dissemination of Open Calls	44
4.8 Scientific Dissemination	50
4.8.1 Publications	50

D9.1 – Dissemination and Communication Strategy

4.8.2 Scientific Conferences	51
4.8.3 Scientific Workshops and Meetings	51
4.9 Partnerships and Synergies	56
5. Stakeholders	58
5.1 Stakeholder Groups	58
5.1.1 Stakeholders on National Level	66
5.1.2 Stakeholders on European Level	68
5.1.3 Stakeholders on International Level	68
5.2 Other Related Associations, Initiatives and Projects	68
6. Multi-channel Communication strategy	69
6.1 Online	69
6.1.1 Website	70
6.1.2 Newsletter and Mailing List	75
6.1.3 E-Journal and Open Access Repository	75
6.2 Printed Promotional Material	75
6.2.1. Brochures	75
6.2.2 Posters and Roll-ups	77
6.2.3 Promotional Stickers	78
6.2.4 Other Promotional Merchandise Articles	79
7. Evaluation and Monitoring of Dissemination and Communication Activities	80
8. Obligations and Requirements for Communication Actions	80
8.1 Information on of EU Funding	80
8.2 Disclaimer excluding Agency and Commission Responsibility	81
8.3 Data Privacy and Legal Notice	82
8.4 Management of Intellectual Property and Open Access	82
8.5 Personal Photographs of People	83
9. Conclusion	83
10. Internal Review	84
10.1 Internal Review 1	84
10.2 Internal Review 2	88
11. Annex	93

List of Figures

FIGURE 1: PLATOON LOGO.....	22
FIGURE 2: SMART CITY.....	22
FIGURE 3: PLATOON LOGO; COLOURED, BLACK, WHITE	23
FIGURE 4: COLOURS, COLOUR TYPOGRAPHY AND TYPOGRAPHY	23
FIGURE 5: PLATOON PARTNERS AND PILOTS MAP	24
FIGURE 6: EU EMBLEM AND BDVA LOGO.....	25
FIGURE 7: PLATOON TWITTER HOMEPAGE	30
FIGURE 8: PLATOON TWITTER ANALYTICS SECTION	31
FIGURE 9: PLATOON TWEETS (PART 1).....	31
FIGURE 10: PLATOON TWEETS (PART 2).....	32
FIGURE 11: PLATOON TWEETS (PART 3).....	33
FIGURE 12: PLATOON LINKEDIN HOMEPAGE (ADMIN VIEW).....	34
FIGURE 13: PLATOON LINKEDIN HOMEPAGE (MEMBERS' VIEW).....	35
FIGURE 14: PLATOON LINKEDIN POSTS	35
FIGURE 15: PLATOON YOUTUBE CHANNEL.....	36
FIGURE 16: TIB'S STAND AT HANNOVER MESSE 2020	43
FIGURE 17: INFORMATION ON POSTPONED HANNOVER MESSE 2020.....	43
FIGURE 18: SUPPORT PROGRAMME (BOTTOM-UP PROJECTS EXECUTION)	48
FIGURE 19: BOTTOM-UP PROJECTS	49
FIGURE 20: STAKEHOLDER COMMUNICATION.....	58
FIGURE 21: PLATOON WEBSITE HOMEPAGE.....	70
FIGURE 22: PLATOON WEBSITE NEWS & EVENTS ON HOMEPAGE	71
FIGURE 23: PLATOON WEBSITE CONTACT SECTION	71
FIGURE 24: PLATOON WEBSITE CONSORTIUM SECTION.....	71
FIGURE 25: PLATOON WEBSITE NEWS & EVENTS SECTION	72
FIGURE 26: BROCHURE (EXTERNAL SIDE)	77
FIGURE 27: BROCHURE (INTERNAL SIDE).....	77
FIGURE 28: PLATOON POSTER VERSION 1.....	78
FIGURE 29: PLATOON POSTER VERSION 2.....	78
FIGURE 30: STICKER VERSION 1.....	79
FIGURE 31: STICKER VERSION 2.....	79

List of Tables

TABLE 1: PLATOON SWOT ANALYSIS.....	12
TABLE 2: COMMUNICATION CHANNELS AND ACTIVITIES.....	20
TABLE 3: PRESS RELEASE MEDIA AND TARGET GROUPS	26
TABLE 4: PLATOON TWITTER ACCOUNT	29
TABLE 5: PLATOON LINKEDIN PROFILE.....	34
TABLE 6: PLATOON YOUTUBE ACCOUNT.....	36
TABLE 7: MAJOR CONFERENCES, EVENTS AND AWARENESS DAYS.....	41
TABLE 8: ACTION PLAN FOR OPEN CALL COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES	45
TABLE 9: JOURNALS.....	51
TABLE 10: SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCES	51
TABLE 11: COMMUNICATION & DISSEMINATION OF THE WORK PACKAGES.....	52

D9.1 – Dissemination and Communication Strategy

TABLE 12: COMMUNICATION OF THE MILESTONES.....	54
TABLE 13: STAKEHOLDER GROUPS	60
TABLE 14: STAKEHOLDER GROUPS ON NATIONAL LEVEL.....	66
TABLE 15: OTHER RELATED PROJECTS.....	69

Terms and Abbreviations

ACRONYM	DESCRIPTION
CA	Consortium Agreement
CMS	Content Management System
CO	Confidential
COSMAG	Comprehensive Architecture for Smart Grid
CTO	Chief Technology Officer
DM	Dissemination Manager
DoA	Description of Action
DSO	Distribution System Operator
EC	European Commission
EM	Exploitation Manager
ESCO	Energy Service Company
FSTP	Financial Support to Third Parties
GA	Grant Agreement
GAM	General Assembly Meeting
H2020	Horizon 2020
ICT	Information and Communication Technology

D9.1 – Dissemination and Communication Strategy

IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
LI	LinkedIn
LSP	Local Service Provider
MVP	Minimum Viable Products
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
PM	Project Manager
PoC	Proof of Concept
PU	Public
QA	Quality Assurance
Q&A	Questions and Answers
R&I	Research and Innovation
RE	Restricted
REN	Renewable Energy
SAB	Stakeholder Advisory Board
SC	Steering Committee
SEO	Search Engine Optimisation
SGAM	Smart Grid Architecture Model
SME	Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises
TM	Technical Manager
TSO	Transmission System Operator

D9.1 – Dissemination and Communication Strategy

TTP	Technology Transfer Program
TW	Twitter
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader
YT	YouTube

Executive Summary

The objective of the deliverable is to outline the strategy for dissemination and communication activities carried out during the project. The deliverable is structured in eight sections addressing different aspects that a communication plan usually details: the strategy from the project to the external audience, the basis for a proper internal communication between the project partners, the elements required to evaluate and measure the results of the communication strategy and finally the obligations and constraints dictated by the EC regarding communication activities in every H2020 project. The document encompasses the external Communication Plan (including Communication strategy, PLATOON key messages, stakeholder groups, dissemination tools and channels) and the internal communication plan (including internal communication procedures, rules and recommendations for a correct use of external communication tools, evaluation and monitoring of the PLATOON dissemination activities, as well as obligations and requirements for communication actions).

This deliverable provides a general communication and dissemination strategy for whereas D9.2 will showcase in greater detail the website and communication materials. The results of D9.1 will be evaluated in D9.3 Dissemination and Communication Report, due in M12, M24, and M36. D9.3 and its updated versions will contain a detailed presentation and evaluation of the communication activities undertaken during the previous period; as well as an updated version of the general communication strategy; and detailed planning for the period ahead. Corrective measures will be implemented when and if necessary, e.g. by adapting and customising the dissemination and communication strategy, in order to maximise its impact.

The general objectives of PLATOON's WP9 are to disseminate effectively the project goals and outcomes, set up efficient tools for the communication towards various stakeholders (scientific communities, industrial stakeholders, energy professionals, data scientists, policy makers, general public, etc.), and exploit synergies in liaisons and collaborations, maximizing thus the visibility and impact of the project.

1. Introduction

The present document acts as a general roadmap for all PLATOON-related communication and dissemination activities. It presents PLATOON's overall communication and dissemination plan (section 2); details how the impact of the PLATOON project will be communicated (section 3) analyses the project's communication methods and tools (section 4) and stakeholder groups (section 5), presents the project's multi-channel communication strategy (section 6); analyses the evaluation and monitoring of dissemination and communication activities (section 7); describes the obligations and requirements for communication actions (section 8).

2. Communication and Dissemination Plan

2.1 Main Goal

The communication and dissemination actions within the context of PLATOON focus on promoting the project's research and educational aspects, including jargon-free, policy- and decision-making messages, to a vast range of stakeholders.

PLATOON (Digital PLAtform and analytical TOOLS for eEnergy) builds a cyber-secure digital platform that allows for large-scale multi-party data exchange, processing and monetisation, all governed by a clear data governance policy. During the project, the necessary analytical toolbox is developed for energy specific applications that can contribute to make the existing energy system more efficient by improving current processes and unleashing new services and business models. Most importantly, all these solutions need to be implemented, and validated using the project's seven large scale pilots. The COSMAG compliant reference platform with flexible capabilities will cover a wide number of challenges and solutions:

- Interoperability to deal with a wide spectrum and heterogeneous data sources, formats, interfaces,
- Data governance and security to answer multiple data owners and providers,
- User friendliness by energy domain experts without deep mathematical knowledge. The toolbox will apply pure mathematical techniques, like statistical characterization, classification, prediction, optimization, to the energy sector needs predictive maintenance and life extension of energy assets, distribution grids optimum management, peak power avoidance and demand side response, efficient end use of energy.

At the end of the project, PLATOON will successfully cover the following business challenges:

- To enhance the role of the energy sector stakeholders to let them reliably, fairly and securely extract knowledge from their own data.
- To foster the new business models in the energy sector using digital technologies.

D9.1 – Dissemination and Communication Strategy

- To enhance the multi-party cooperation between technology providers and data owners.
- To contribute to standardization of the energy management systems by assessing whether current standards offer the proper roles interfaces to enable business processes, including new ones and identify where new standards may be needed, according to the COSMAG reference.

Consequently, all communication and dissemination messages will be customised to address all aspects of the project and communicate the project's progress and output to a vast range of stakeholders, who are analysed in Section 5.

2.2 Objectives

The communication and dissemination plan and activities focus on highlighting the scientific and technological objectives of the project. The communication will be fully aligned with the progress of the scientific and technical WPs of the project, aiming to reflect their latest status in the communication activities and channels. As such, WP9 activities will focus on demonstrating the progress achieved as per the project's objectives;

- *O1. To define and promote a COSMAG-compliant reference architecture.* This objective defines the requirements and specifications of the PLATOON reference platform and conducts an analysis of the project's pilots that represents a wide range of problems and needs of the energy sector. Use and business cases that can be mapped with the COSMAG and SGAM references will be defined.
- *O2. To design and develop an open, vendor-independent data governance scheme based on IDS (International Data Space) principles which guarantee data sovereignty and privacy for all the stakeholders.* The governance framework defines the secure data exchange between stakeholders (consumers and providers) equipped with a compliant endpoint, or data connector. This exchange environment will be evolved into an open and trusted data marketplace enabling data and service use transactions to be extended to external stakeholders. PLATOON's governance model focuses on secure data exchange, guaranteeing data sovereignty, in line with IDS principles and GDPR. The communication and dissemination will focus on all angles pertaining to PLATOON's Energy Data Marketplace.
- *O3. To develop a specific interoperability layer that enables heterogenous, bulky and high speed-data transfer from the pilots to the PLATOON platform.* Interoperability represents a key challenge, dealing with very heterogeneous Energy platforms that differ in terms of technologies, communications protocols and data models. Based on international on-going standardisation initiatives, the interoperability layer will be focused on the provisioning of technological-agnostic Open API and adoption of common data models in the domain of Energy and Big Data: this will enable and facilitate both the development of ad-hoc connectors and the data transfer and harmonisation of the pilot datasets that will be further processed and analysed by

D9.1 – Dissemination and Communication Strategy

the different components (e.g. toolbox) provided within the scope of the PLATOON project.

- *O4. To develop, deploy, integrate and validate a data analytics toolbox easy to be used by energy experts and customized to solve the specific needs of the energy infrastructures operators and data owners.* The PLATOON project will develop a Data Analytics Toolbox that will integrate the knowledge acquired and/or the algorithms developed by the technological partners of the Consortium in the solution of the mentioned problems. It is intended that experts in the energy domain, but not experts in data analytics can solve their own problems through the PLATOON Data Analytics Toolbox.
- *O5. To design and implement local real time processing capabilities in the edge to provide local smartness and alleviate the data transfer to the PLATOON components deployed in the cloud.* PLATOON proposes to develop and install local smart solutions within energy infrastructures with enough intelligence to process the measured data in real time and provide and send to the cloud magnitudes with more content and information (knowledge) but less amount of data. Thus, PLATOON will develop hardware solutions that will embed data analytics algorithms. These solutions will be implemented and validated in the Smart Grids with integrated renewable energy devices, and End Use of Energy pilots, for a better network operation and for a health diagnosis of the critical energy assets.

2.3 SWOT Analysis

The mission of the PLATOON project, the context in which it operates, and the composition of its consortium; all lead to several unique strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats regarding its communication and dissemination objectives. These unique characteristics are analysed in the SWOT Table 1 as follows:

Table 1: PLATOON SWOT Analysis

STRENGTHS (helpful & internal)	WEAKNESSES (harmful & internal)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● experienced management and enough resources ● involvement of experienced professionals ● project's unique approach ● project's long-term vision ● consortium encompasses a large network of stakeholders including existing Research Infrastructures, possessing strong established dissemination channels 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● consortium's large size and diversity ● tailoring messages to diverse audiences may be difficult ● news worthiness ● difficulty in reaching audiences beyond academia such as policy makers, the general public. ● difficulty in framing (horizontally vs vertically) our communication ● lack of involvement,

D9.1 – Dissemination and Communication Strategy

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● unresponsive partners ● Technical complexity of the project not easy to understand for a wider audience
OPPORTUNITIES (helpful & external)	THREATS (harmful & external)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● spin news values in our favour (e.g. the message "investing in culture is investing in future") ● involvement of truly international actors ● possibility to create "something different" from scratch ● reaching out to less well represented countries such as newer member states ● present and justify investment in research to the public 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● academic approach to media attention ● bureaucracy ● (too) specific and jargon based information ● lack of coordination, leading to message "silos" rather than a single coherent message ● "flat" news feed; failure to continuously keep stakeholders informed.

Our SWOT analysis indicates that PLATOON has a unique opportunity to reach a very wide and varied audience to disseminate information about the project's innovative research, use cases, pilots and technology transfer activities. However, the project will only be able to realise this potential if it can efficiently implement the suggested communication and dissemination strategy proposed in this deliverable by collaborating intensively with consortium partners, identified stakeholders (e.g. affiliated projects), and by framing its messages in a coherent, well-coordinated manner and in accordance to the needs and interests of the various relevant stakeholder communities, going thus really beyond the technical part to make it more interesting for wider audiences.

2.4 Communication and Dissemination Principles

This section presents a set of five basic principles, on which PLATOON's dissemination and communication strategy is based. The adherence to these principles will ensure that the project can fully exploit its strengths and opportunities, while diminishing and managing identified potential weaknesses and threats as outlined in the SWOT analysis here above.

1. Adaptability. Given the scope of the project and the specific themes involved, the communication strategy needs to be comprehensive enough to cover the project, while being adaptable to the project's various research themes and stakeholder communities. For example, specific channels are to be used to reach target groups, and dissemination materials may have to be tailored to the needs of different end users.

D9.1 – Dissemination and Communication Strategy

2. *Flexibility.* As per the previous pillar, PLATOON's communication needs to be flexible and open, in order to create a responsive framework to changing needs and challenges.

3. *Dynamism.* The dynamic element is the natural consequence of the two points above. A dynamic strategy is a key to maximise the impact of PLATOON.

4. *Tailoring of messages/usage of appropriate language.* PLATOON needs to be able to communicate appropriately to academic audiences in a variety of fields, to industrial target sectors and specific segments of the energy value chains, as well as to decision makers and the public at large. To achieve this, PLATOON will follow a multi-layered communication strategy that formulates core messages tailored to the needs and expectations of the various target audiences, and expressed in appropriate language (specialised, technical communication vs. plain, jargon-free communication; ideally, in an engaging storytelling style, rather than descriptive).

5. *Exploitation of synergies with a vast range of stakeholders:* PLATOON addresses a vast range of topics, such as data science, big data analytics, policy making, start-ups and SMEs, business models, pilots, climate change, renewable energies, smart cities, smart buildings, data marketplaces, etc. As such, the project can draw upon a plethora of expertise, networks and dissemination and communication channels that are already in existence at partner institutions and related projects and that can reach the specific subject communities with which PLATOON wishes to engage. PLATOON needs to exploit to the fullest the synergistic effects that can be achieved by building bridges between these existing resources and must avoid a duplication of effort. Therefore, achieving better coordination and cross-fertilisation of existing communication and dissemination activities is central to PLATOON's dissemination and communication strategy.

2.5 Internal Rules and Procedures for a proper use of Communication Tools

Another important asset in terms of communication strategy within the project is to have homogeneous formats related to project deliverables, documents, presentations or any other item eventually produced. For this purpose, PLATOON has produced different templates available for the consortium partners for main formats, e.g. .doc (for documents and deliverables), .ppt (for PLATOON presentations).

TIB, as the Lead of WP9, guides all partners as per their communication activities pertaining to the project. This is implemented by sharing internal communication and dissemination guidelines for internal and external communication and providing consulting regarding all aspects of communication, e.g. appropriate use of social media and communication content during the project. Furthermore, TIB will lead and host a monthly telco focusing on WP9, to guide the partners as per communication and dissemination activities, e.g. participation in conferences, regular content creation (e.g. blog posts on topics relevant to PLATOON), and

D9.1 – Dissemination and Communication Strategy

active engagement of all PLATOON partners in the communication and dissemination campaigns led by TIB. Internal rules and procedures are listed and can be accessed by the consortium partners in the shared google folder of WP9. The rules and procedures can be updated and adjusted during the project, in order to maximise the impact of the communication activities. Moreover, TIB will regularly communicate the rules and procedures to the consortium partners via the general mailing list of the project. Throughout the project duration, TIB will explore the possibility to set up separate mailing lists per stakeholder category pertaining to the internal environment of the project, in order to ensure targeted, efficient and impactful communication. More specifically, the networks of associated partners, stakeholder board members, mentors and ambassadors will have separate mailing lists, via which TIB will share relevant rules and procedures as well as communication content and project updates.

2.6 External Communication

A careful design of the action plan for communication is critical in order to contribute to the success of the PLATOON project, which is not confined to inner research and innovation tasks developed by PLATOON partners but to outreach, support and funding of external companies through different instruments as the main objective of the project. During the first four months of the PLATOON timeline in WP9 a set of tools, methodologies and communication flows addressing the external audience have been thoroughly defined and tailored to the project, considering the existence of a main objective, and multiple secondary goals specifically defined according to different local, national and European levels, diversity of targets or the level of interaction sought. Dissemination actions envisaged in PLATOON will be directed by a common axis drawn according to the general aim of the project, expressed in the DoA.

The PLATOON project concept entails the launch and management, following EC standards, of two Open Calls, in order to select the top 13 disruptive bottom-up projects that will be accepted into 2 different Technology Transfer Programmes (TTP) and to accompany the Bottom-up projects selected with a full range of services during the two 9-months-long TTPs. Thus, PLATOON will boost cross fertilisation between SMEs, stakeholders from the application sectors and operators of the energy and computer science sector. Direct and indirect support to SMEs will be provided in order to accelerate new ideas all along the energy value chain, from idea emergence up to the demonstration and the internationalization stages with a focus on the creation of new value chains in the energy sector. Therefore, driven by this main aim, specific communication messages will be underpinned by several main concepts:

1. Transmit the opportunity to broadcast their needs at a local, national and EU level throughout the PLATOON project to the end user community in the energy and computer science sectors.

D9.1 – Dissemination and Communication Strategy

2. Understand the technology as the key asset capable of bridging the gaps derived from the end user needs.
3. Support the creation and implementation of new value chain models in the energy sector by means of digital technologies applied to the mentioned sectors.
4. Provide financial support especially to SMEs in the energy and ICT sectors that focus on boosting technology maturation, testing, market adoption and internationalisation.
5. PLATOON outcomes can be adopted as a valid reference for the definition and implementation of forthcoming policy frameworks or strategic plans at national and/or European level.

2.7 Key Messages

The main and more powerful messages of the PLATOON project will be defined during its own development; once WPs deliver the goals established in the GA and the deliverables are completed. The nature of the messages will be targeted to different audiences and will have a different theme adapted to each of the objectives listed in the GA and consequently in this Communication Plan.

The key messages will be revised during the project to better reflect the status of the project and will be adapted to the specific needs and interest areas of the pertinent categories of stakeholders. Furthermore, special attention will be given to articulate these key messages, ideally, under a clear narrative about the project; e.g. example: what's the problem, how the project solves it. From the very beginning, and until the first deliverables will be accessible and ready to disseminate, the key messages will be focused on the major assets of the project:

1) End users, policy makers and general public pillar key messages

- PLATOON will communicate its beneficial role for the society in terms of fostering societal progress.
- PLATOON will promote a better society with a more adapted and integrated interactive energy sector based on optimized real-time energy system management.
- PLATOON will contribute to answering several ethical, legal, economic and industrial benchmarking questions
- PLATOON will contribute to identify the regulatory needs and gaps applicable to the digitalisation of the energy sector in the EU.
- PLATOON will be showcased in related events (conferences, workshops, webinars, summer schools, etc.) in order to improve awareness about the needs and gaps in the energy and computer science domains.

D9.1 – Dissemination and Communication Strategy

2) Technical expertise pillar key messages

Synergies with standardisation and regulatory bodies: PLATOON will coordinate workshops with stakeholders to identify gaps and needs in the regulatory and standardisation related to the energy sector and its digitalisation. As identified in T8.4, Regulatory and policy framework, lessons learned and recommendations, (M19–M36), PLATOON will identify priorities for standardisation and engagement in standardization activities and develop recommendations for regulation bodies. The project will provide input into the relevant groups and working bodies inside the European standardization organization CEN, CENELEC and ETSI, and will expand the knowledge base to ensure standards remain relevant to emerging technologies; within the project it is expected that there will be a focus on larger infrastructure installations and interoperability between such systems. The project will develop suitable relationships with the relevant bodies and encourage participation at events across the globe. The deliverables within this activity will consist of both consortium and public documentation and presentation. TIB will support T8.4, led by UDGA and implement respective communication campaigns to showcase the synergies with the standardisation bodies. In this content TIB will offer the organisation of webinars with these topics, will conduct interviews with the stakeholders of the standardisation and regulatory bodies and propose other communication measures.

3) Business expertise pillar key messages

PLATOON will work on removing or cutting down the non-technical barriers in the diffusion of energy solutions in real-life applications, engaging and supporting thus different stakeholders of the energy sector value chain, starting from electricity producers and their suppliers (equipment and component manufacturers, engineering firms, operation service providers, ICT companies etc.),, passing through the distributor, the aggregator, the ESCO, the electricity retailers until the end user.

One of the most relevant non-technical barriers that should be addressed by the dissemination activities for PLATOON is the “data access challenge”. Only companies at the top of the value chain, such as utilities, renewable energy plant operators and some OEMs (the “Data owners”) have access to the data collected from the energy facilities: smart grids, wind farms, solar plants, energy consumers (factories, buildings). Therefore, they are the only players that are presently working on extracting value out of data. Consequently, most European components suppliers, engineering firms or ICT (Information and communication Technologies) companies cannot analyse and learn from data, missing that way the opportunity to improve their competitiveness and increase the added value of the products through digitization.

WP9, represented by TIB, participates in all business-related activities of the PLATOON project, including telcos of WP1, for the business case definition, the business requirements. In this case, the objective is to enable and activate the communication workflows processes which will improve the coordination among stakeholders and requirements for services for

D9.1 – Dissemination and Communication Strategy

optimized interactions will be defined. Moreover, TIB will collaborate closely with WP8, business models and exploitation, and integrate the output of this work package in the communication activities planned within the context of WP9 (press releases, webinar, planned social media campaigns etc.). In this context TIB will facilitate the access to new business models and new market opportunities for the stakeholders across the energy value chain and facilitate the networking between SMEs, large companies and potential end users in the energy sector. Via the planned training and capacity building programme, TIB will aim to offer guidelines for young entrepreneurs that resume exemplary Best-Practices for establishing business models on a national/European/international level that takes into consideration the very diverse market (hardware/software/systems integration) and applications in the energy sector.

4) Ethical, legal and socioeconomic expertise pillar key messages

T1.5: Legal & ethics requirements will be considered and respected in all communication activities planned and implemented within the context of WP9. Furthermore, TIB will explore the possibility to set up mailing lists addressing the specific requirements of the distinct communities, which are external to the PLATOON consortium, e.g. SMEs and start-ups, energy experts, policy makers etc. and which can be used to share project related updates. Furthermore, the project's newsletter will be shared with the registered stakeholders every six months during the project. The newsletter strategy and content are analysed in section 4.4 and 6.1.5.

3. Communicating the Impact of the PLATOON Project

The communication of the PLATOON project will focus on addressing the expected impacts listed in the work programme and described in the GA. In this regard, the communication message across all channels (website, social media, etc.) will be customised accordingly to highlight the following aspects of the project and the impact achieved throughout its duration.

The communication message will highlight the effective integration of relevant digital technologies in the energy sector resulting in integrated value chains. Webinars, blog posts, interviews and dedicated brochures will showcase PLATOON's lightweight reference architecture and how it will effectively integrate already existing digital platforms from the different participating organisations, including the interoperability layer that enables data exchange between platforms creating integrated value chains, the data governance schema that ensures data security, privacy and sovereignty. The data analytics toolbox will be presented at a specific website section and brochure. Likewise, each one of the seven large-scale pilots will be analysed on the respective website section and brochure. The website and brochures, including all digital and printed communication material, will be regularly updated throughout the project's duration, in order to reflect the latest status.

D9.1 – Dissemination and Communication Strategy

Furthermore, the communication message will be tailored to showcase how the PLATOON project will enhance energy asset management, increase consumer participation and innovative network management and create new data-driven business models and opportunities and innovative energy services. The communication activities will highlight how PLATOON contributes to increasing the use of renewable energy and increased energy efficiency based on optimised energy asset management, offering access to cheaper and sustainable energy for end users and maximising social welfare.

Besides the scientific communication focusing on high level, technical and data science topics, the communication activities will focus on strengthening links with other programmes and initiatives, supported by regional, national and European policies and funds, and thereby reaching out to a vast range of stakeholders. PLATOON has obtained letters of support representing a total of 7 supportive parties and ambassadors across the European energy sector. Also, PLATOON will establish an Advisory Board formed of 5 partners that will provide impartial advice. PLATOON will launch 2 open calls to engage with at least 13 SMEs and start-ups to develop new products and services. The PLATOON community will be built to engage supportive partners and ambassadors that will promote the project across different countries. Finally, the PLATOON project will make use of BRIDGE and ECTP initiatives and the networks established by BDVA and the energy specific clusters, where many of the PLATOON partners are key players, to strengthen links with other regional, national and European programmes and ensure a widespread impact of the project. The additional supportive partners engaged (Target Value: 20), the ambassadors (Target Value: 6), the external exploitation partners (Target Value: 20) and the number of collaborations with other regional, national and European programmes (Target Value: 50) will be featured in distinct sections on the website. Communication campaigns will be implemented throughout the project's duration aiming to highlight the project's impact in relation to its various angles and stakeholder groups.

The involvement of PLATOON partners in other initiatives such as BRIDGE and ECTP and other organizations such as the BDVA, Fraunhofer's Big Data Alliance, and the Industrial Data Space association provides an attractive environment to facilitate and attract innovation capacity by universities, research centres and companies and create new market opportunities. In this regard, synergies will be formed consisting of organisation of joint events, conferences and workshops, joint webinars and cross posting of press releases and other important project announcements.

PLATOON is fully aligned with climate change EU strategies through resource-efficient low-carbon solutions based on the introduction of smart grids and optimising the operation of the whole energy value chain from generation, distribution to consumption. Specifically, PLATOON contributes to the cost-effective management of generation assets, better integration of renewable energy sources, and optimisation of distribution grid operations, system inefficiencies reduction, energy consumption reduction and contribution to the introduction of smart grids. The climate change angle will be prominently featured in the communication activities of the project, e.g. social media and content for blog posts,

D9.1 – Dissemination and Communication Strategy

webinars etc., highlighting how the PLATOON project will foster the successful roll out of smart grids in the European electricity system, encouraging the citizen participation in the energy system, establishing a bilateral relationship between consumers and energy providers. This conceptual innovation will certainly have a positive welcome and will be translated into a significant acceleration of the introduction of smart grids in the European electricity system.

4. Communication Methods and Tools

The table here below lists the planned communication methods and tools. Their content will be regularly updated in order to reflect the latest status of the project. The progress achieved as per the estimated scale/ audience will be reported in the iterations of D9.3.

Table 2: Communication Channels and Activities

CHANNEL	COMMUNICATION ACTIVITY	ESTIMATED SCALE/ AUDIENCE
Project Website	Project Website.	10,000 visits yearly
Webinars, Podcasts, Online space	Webinars / podcasts (e.g., summaries of research results for citizens, reports from conferences, interviews with key figures of the relevant industries, success stories), video tutorials.	>100 participants & 100 YouTube views per webinar
Leaflets, Posters	Distribution of promotional material at outreach events, min. 20,000 leaflets needed.	>10 international events
Press releases	in various languages, via the press offices and media contacts of all partners, also via CORDIS (Community Research and Development Information Service)	>8 press releases in total, each in several languages, EU-wide
Mailing list(s)	Forum for stakeholders from target domains for communication re. the European data economy and the TRUSTS platform.	>2,000 newsletter subscribers at the end of the project
Social media	Multiplying communication efforts by using social media like Twitter and LinkedIn.	1,000 followers on Twitter 15,000 impressions across platforms
Meetings	Meetings and workshops.	>20 events

TIB oversees the production of a diverse set of dissemination tools, both online and offline, that are the main instruments for the PLATOON partners for a correct performance of communication actions.

4.1 General Dissemination

General dissemination aims at heightening the awareness of the project to establish stakeholder and cooperation networks, including

- Network of stakeholders: map and contact stakeholders at local/regional basis (website, press release, direct contact)
- Networking with other initiatives and projects: map events, initiatives, projects, establish contact (EU, national, local)
- Participate in events (local, national, EU-level)
- Map mass media (energy and data science magazines etc.)
- Record media impressions at the “Press Section” of the website.

This is currently related to the first phase goal of increasing the awareness of the project in order to establish the proper working relations with stakeholders and other initiatives etc. But also, in relation to the second phase goal of increasing the understanding of the project among relevant stakeholders (database, capacity building activities, planning concept) and in a close interaction with the other WPs.

4.2 Visual Identity

The complete PLATOON visual identity is designed, that is centralized on a clear PLATOON logo concept and a colour pantone. The project identity aims at reinforcing the project’s external image and ensuring a transversal coherence between all project communication channels. Basically, it includes the project logo, documents layout and the project message. Using PLATOON’s logo beyond the limits inherent to the project and its communication is not allowed.

Project Logo

The logo has been prepared based on the criteria that it should be easily scalable, easy to reproduce, memorable and distinctive, and usable on a variety of media.

The PLATOON logo is a combination of essential concepts that surround the industries involved in the project, i.e. renewable energy, data science, digitalization, and smart homes. Hereby, the green colour symbolises climate protection, sustainability and renewable energy, whereas the purple colour stands for innovation and knowledge. There are two diamonds, whose frames are coloured in green and purple, and both figures are hooked together. To the inside of the logo, both diamonds are formed in a way that the interface between these two figures forms a house. Inside of the white house is a window that consists of four yellow 2x2 boxes. The house symbolizes smart homes and the yellow window stands for energy that has been provided to the building. Inside the frames of the green and purple diamonds, there are many zeros and ones, coloured in green or purple respectively. These numbers symbolise the digitalisation trend within the energy sector.

Figure 1: PLATOON Logo

Below the logo is the name of the project “PLATOON” written in capital letters. All letters are in a dark blue except for the two O’s that are coloured in green or purple respectively. Below “PLATOON” is the full name of the project, written in light purple, smaller size and normal letters: “Digital platform and analytic tools for energy”.

The overall picture of the logo is that PLATOON can be understood as an interface between the energy sector and the innovative digitalization trend and the final goal of this project is to provide modern, smart, interconnected households, industries and buildings with clean, safe and inexpensive energy.

Figure 2: Smart City

Figure 3: PLATOON Logo; coloured, black, white

Figure 4: Colours, Colour Typography and Typography

COLORS

COLORS TYPOGRAPHY

TYPOGRAPHY

Roboto Bold - Title

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ1234567890
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz1234567890

Roboto Regular - Paragraph

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ1234567890
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz1234567890

Figure 5: PLATOON Partners and Pilots Map

Project Message

The project message is a sentence that should clearly and simply state what the project is trying to achieve, and which should be constantly communicated to target groups, for example by including it in projects’ promotional material such as flyers, website, press releases etc. The message agreed within the project consortium is the “PLATOON, Digital PLatform and analytic TOOLS for eNergy”. It will be explored during the project, whether further messages will be used for communication purposes.

An easily recognisable (visual) identity of the project is essential to achieve best communication results. A Visual Identity Guide is created and made available to project partners to apply during communication and dissemination activities. It is of high importance to use these visual tools coherently.

Visual tools:

- project logo (in English)
- project molino/roll-up (in English and can be translated in national languages)
- templates (ppt, project newsletter, press release, scientific conference presentation, policy brief, paper, H2020 reporting/deliverable, etc.)
- general flyer/project brochure (in English and in national languages of the beneficiaries)
- project poster (in English and in national languages)
- general project website (in English)
- Grant Agreement number – partners are requested to use the project GA number in all their external communication and dissemination materials, together with

D9.1 – Dissemination and Communication Strategy

- EU emblem and the accompanying text of: “This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 872592”.

Figure 6: EU Emblem and BDVA Logo

As indicated in the contractual information, any communication activity and result funded by the grant must display the EU emblem and include the following text to indicate that said result was generated with the assistance of financial support and that it reflects the author's view only:

- For communication activities: *“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 871481”.*
- Disclaimer for both: *“This [insert type of result] reflects only the author’s views and the European Commission does not accept any responsibility for use that may be made of the information it contains.”*

When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have the appropriate visibility and the following guidelines will be maintained throughout the project’s duration:

- Graphics guide to the European emblem can be accessed at: <http://publications.europa.eu/code/en/en-5000100.htm>
- Originals for reproduction are also available for downloading at: http://europa.eu/about-eu/basic-information/symbols/flag/index_en.htm

The project Partners are required to use the logos, colours of the Visual Identity Guide and the templates – some of which are always listed above – developed in the framework of WP9 . In order to set a common visual line for all dissemination elements, a short PLATOON visual identity manual has been released, which is communicated to the Consortium partners. When the colour background does not allow good visibility of the logo, a white background or a black background version of the logo should be used according to the aesthetics of the document. The logo must be used in a black and white version in exceptional cases. Please find more detailed guidelines in D9.2.

4.3 Press Releases

Press releases will be led by TIB that serves as Communication Lead directing and offering consulting for the communication activities of all the PLATOON partners, pertaining to PLATOON. Moreover, press releases can be issued by all partners during the project coinciding with important milestones like launch of the open calls, platform releases, local or European events, and achievement of other project milestones. TIB will ensure that the

D9.1 – Dissemination and Communication Strategy

press releases fulfil the required high-quality criteria and will be published at the project’s website, at CORDIS, at the websites of other project partners and collaborators, including online and print media at the level of the Consortium and beyond. The press releases will be targeted at key stakeholders (e.g. SMEs, relevant local authority departments, local and national media, managing authorities and other funders, TSOs, DSOs, ESCOs, Aggregators, end users, EU Commission, and energy agencies). TIB will actively follow up the releases to assure maximum coverage. The project will involve several press releases and articles in local newspapers and magazines.

Considering that the project will also perform substantial technical work with respect to the coordination and exploitation of information and knowledge, a substantial number of papers and presentations in conferences and publications in journals and magazines is further envisaged (please refer to the table below).

Table 3: Press Release Media and Target Groups

MEDIUM	TARGET GROUPS	GEOGRAPHICAL OUTREACH
Presentations to conferences	Research & Academia, Central Governments, Policy Makers, Technologies Industry, NGOs, Energy Agencies, Public Authorities,	International
Publications to business magazines	Governments, Policy Makers, Technology industries, NGOs, Energy Agencies, Public Authorities, Business community, supportive structures and networks	National
Press releases to newspapers	All	Local/ National
Peer-reviewed journal papers	Research & Academia	International

The first press release of the project will be published when the project’s website will be online, in order to maximise the views of the website and increase the number of newsletter subscribers. This press release will focus on sharing key project info and including quotes of the consortium partners as per their expectations of the project in terms of output and impact. At the same time, a Twitter and LinkedIn campaign will be implemented, using the quotes of the press release and directing to the project’s website, aiming to incite interest and spur active engagement of stakeholders with the project.

TIB will coordinate a monthly WP9 telco, in which representatives of all the partners will participate and attend the monthly telcos of other WPs. The aim is to identify the appropriate timing for the preparation and release of the upcoming press releases,

D9.1 – Dissemination and Communication Strategy

reflecting key project milestones. Articles and media impressions will be continuously recorded in the press section of the website and reported in the iterations of D9.3.

4.4 Social Media Strategy

Social media has become a very popular means of disseminating information fast across heterogeneous target groups. These channels serve on-demand access to content anytime, anywhere, on any digital device. To extend the project target audience (especially to involve the great public and not only sector experts) PLATOON is integrating these media tools strategically in the communication activities. Twitter and LinkedIn have been selected as the most appropriate social networks to promote the project achievements, news and outcomes. TIB will act as a moderator of both social profiles, that means control and filter inadequate contents and monitor the suitability and relevance of information to be published.

The project social media strategy drafted at M3 focuses on strengthening the project presence mainly in the European social media, but also in the international social media. The social media activities will help to increase the project's impact and relay information as widely as possible. Considered as a powerful interactive media tool, they will serve as a platform to discuss, comment, consult and suggest research and policy topics with different stakeholders at different levels, while focusing on communication and disseminating the output of the project.

The social media strategy aims at:

- Identifying and approaching persons and organizations that are already active in fields related to the project activities (e.g. professionals in LinkedIn).
- Disseminate the project's news, output, related activities, and results as well as include calls for action.
- Engaging social media followers, preferably by directing them to the PLATOON website.
- Creating interactive forums at European and national scale with external stakeholders.

Actions to be performed in this context include:

- Identifying and approaching the relevant persons and organizations.
- Join relevant LinkedIn professional groups in order to promote the project.
- Regular social media posts (e.g. 1 tweet per day, blog posts published on a weekly basis and disseminated via TW and LI) aiming at informing and initiating discussions/debates/feedback.
- Social Media Campaigns: boosting posts towards the target group. Such campaigns will be customised to the project's milestones. For instance, at the start of the project the campaign "Meet the consortium" will be featured, including interviews of all project partners focusing on their role, expectations and importance of the

D9.1 – Dissemination and Communication Strategy

PLATOON project. Another campaign will be the launch of the open calls. All campaigns will be informative and increase the visibility of the project and its achievements.

- TIB has asked all consortium partners to further disseminate PLATOON related content via their organisations' social media accounts, with the objective to further increase organically the visibility of the project.

Measures to grow social media accounts

The social media strategy will be regularly evaluated and adjusted when necessary in order to maximise the impact of all communication activities and will be developed as follows:

- Initially, social media accounts of organisations and persons active in the domains areas relevant to PLATOON are, since M1, identified and followed. Relevant content will be disseminated by PLATOON's social media accounts, i.e. events relevant for energy stakeholders organised by **various Directorates of the European Commission**, f.e. **Energy4Europe** (@Energy4Europe), **EU Climate Action** (@EUClimateAction), **EU Environment** (@EU_ENV), **Horizon 2020** (@EU_H2020), **EU Research Results** (@Cordis_EU), **EUinmyRegion** (@EUinmyRegion), **EU ScienceHub** (@EU_ScienceHub), **EU Agriculture** (EUAgri), **EUScience & Innovation** (@EUScienceInnov), **INEA** (@inea_eu), **EU Energy News** (@EUEnergyNews), **EESC Energy, Transport & Digital** (@EESC_TEN) and **Digital Single Market** (@DSMeu), **EIT InnoEnergy** (@InnoEnergyEU), focusing on crossposting of relevant content. TIB aims to engage these stakeholders with respect to the PLATOON project, by sharing relevant content online, besides project related activities and news. This list will be further enriched during the project.
- Relevant organisations and persons will be invited to connect with the project either through social media or through personal messages. This will include the stakeholders involved in the project and press distribution lists.
- Followers can also be reached through so-called twitter ads¹ (paid advertisement), which can be targeted specifically at potential followers. TIB will explore the possibility to implement Twitter ads campaigns during critical milestones of the project, e.g. launch of open calls, aiming thus to increase the visibility of the project and the numbers of followers.
- As per LinkedIn, posts will be published via the project's company page. Project partners who are active on LinkedIn, will be invited to write from their own personal accounts posts² and articles³ related to PLATOON, in order to increase the project's visibility. Moreover, project stakeholders and consortium partners will be regularly invited to like and reshare content published directly from the PLATOON LinkedIn company page.

¹ Cf. <https://business.twitter.com/en/solutions/twitter-ads.html>

² Cf. <https://www.linkedin.com/help/linkedin/answer/434/posting-and-sharing-content-overview>

³ Cf. <https://www.linkedin.com/help/linkedin/answer/47538/publish-articles-on-linkedin?lang=en>

D9.1 – Dissemination and Communication Strategy

- To maintain active engagement with online followers and subscribers, it is crucial to regularly publish high quality and informative posts via all social media accounts of the project. TIB has committed to prepare one high quality tweet per working day, while actively liking and retweeting from other relevant accounts. At least one blog post will be published on the project’s website on a weekly basis, which will be promoted via a customised tweet and LinkedIn post.

4.4.1 Project-specific Twitter Account

The project specific Twitter account⁴ (@PLATOON_EU) was set up before the official start of the project and is now used to inform the broader community about both technical and other, project and stakeholder related information.

Table 4: PLATOON Twitter Account

TWITTER		
	Twitter Account: @Platoon_EU Official Hashtag: #platoonh2020 #platoonproject #platoonenergy	Use of TW will focus on broadcasting relevant PLATOON news, calls, events, and partners activity, in real-time if possible (a.e. Live action of a PLATOON partner in an external event).

The content of the tweets comprises news about the PLATOON project, upcoming events in which either PLATOON partners or followed key partners are directly involved in, presentation of the consortium partners f.e. via interviews or quotes from the representatives, as well as promotion of EU activities and energy-related topics. The main Twitter strategy is to present the PLATOON project to relevant stakeholders as f.e. energy companies, EU Commission among others, to generate as many followers as possible and to reach a broad audience. This can be achieved by tagging partners with many followers, by reposting other energy-related topics, or similar topics as f.e. data science, climate change or environment, plus activities in which the EU is involved. The TIB set the goal of 1 high quality tweet per working day; tweets prepared by TIB can be accessed directly in the media tab⁵ of the project’s twitter account. At the same time, energy related news and topics (e.g. from EU institutions) are daily retweeted and liked by the project’s account. All PLATOON partners are followed, as well as different energy-related EU instances, or other accounts related to energy, technology, smart cities, computer science, innovation and research, climate and ecology among others.

⁴ Cf. https://twitter.com/PLATOON_EU

⁵ Cf. https://twitter.com/PLATOON_EU/media

Figure 7: PLATOON Twitter Homepage

PLATOON Project
@PLATOON_EU

This @EU_H2020 project aims to digitalise the #energy sector w/ the adoption of data analytics, edge computing & AI. Comm by @AlexandraGaratz & @FribusMichael.
[Biografie übersetzen](#)

📍 Hanover, Lower Saxony 📅 Seit Oktober 2019 bei Twitter

82 Folge ich 90 Follower

Tweets Tweets und Antworten Medien Gefällt mir

📌 Angehefteter Tweet

PLATOON Project @PLATOON_EU · 2 Std.

PLATOON supports #SmartCities 🇩🇪: f.e. in Italy 🇮🇹 we optimise the end use of #energy ⚡ by

- ✓ #power peak consumption characterisation
- ✓ load consumption #data pattern recognition & benchmarking
- ✓ energy consumption forecast

Stay tuned for more!
[#innovation](#) [#Industry40](#) [#AI](#)

KEEP IN TOUCH

- 🐦 @PLATOON_EU
- 🌐 PLATOON.eu
- 🌐 platoon-project.eu
- 📺 PLATOON H2020 Project

Figure 8: PLATOON Twitter Analytics Section

Figure 9: PLATOON Tweets (Part 1)

D9.1 – Dissemination and Communication Strategy

Figure 10: PLATOON Tweets (Part 2)

PLATOON Project @PLATOON_EU · 18. Feb.
 The #H2020 project PLATOON will offer access to cheaper and #sustainableenergy for #energy consumers and maximise #socialwelfare.

More about the H2020 project here bit.ly/25ALgu2.

#BigData #SmartCities #DataScience #Industry40 #ArtificialIntelligence

OWI-Lab und 9 weitere

4 10

PLATOON Project @PLATOON_EU · 11. Feb.
 PLATOON aims to deploy distributed/ edge processing and #DataAnalytics technologies for optimized real-time #energysystem management in a simple way for the #energy domain expert.

Want to know more? This way [bit.ly/2UIJF72!](https://bit.ly/2UIJF72)
 #H2020 #sustainability #AI #renewables

Cluster de Energía und 3 weitere

7 11

PLATOON Project @PLATOON_EU · 17. Feb.
 PLATOON drives forward the #digitalisation of the #energytransition: digitalisation enables higher levels of operational excellence with the adoption of disrupting #technology.

Find out more here bit.ly/2UXvBXf.
 #ClimateAction #Sustainability #energy #H2020

TIB und 4 weitere

4 10

PLATOON Project @PLATOON_EU · 10. Feb.
 The PLATOON architecture and components are valuable for different stakeholders like #electricity suppliers, distributors, aggregators, the #ESCO and end users.

More on this here bit.ly/2ULIDZ7.

#renewableenergy #AI #energysector #EU2020 #innovation

8 9

PLATOON Project @PLATOON_EU · 13. Feb.
 PLATOON will reinforce the #EU efforts for modernisation of the European #electricity grid, because it focuses the attention to new #smartgrids services through #data knowledge exploitation.

See here bit.ly/2Snopy1.
 #H2020 #sustainableenergy #AI #innovation

Tecnalia und 3 weitere

8 9

PLATOON Project @PLATOON_EU · 7. Feb.
 The PLATOON #H2020 project will be validated in 7 pilots in 4 countries:

- 🇧🇪 Belgium
- 🇪🇸 Spain
- 🇮🇹 Italy
- 🇷🇸 Serbia

that provide real #energy #BigData cases. Find out more here bit.ly/39r1rQn.
 #AI #renewableenergy #DataScience @CORDIS_EU @EU_H2020

TIB und 5 weitere

21 18

D9.1 – Dissemination and Communication Strategy

4.4.2 LinkedIn Company Page

The current project specific LinkedIn company page⁶ was set up before the official start of the project. The focus of the LinkedIn company page consists in serving as a platform to disseminate project news, which is posted on the website in the form of blog posts, at the level of LinkedIn. Project news and updates are communicated regularly, so that this company page serves as a platform for discussion, interaction, collection of information, and communication of the project outputs, to experts, e.g. research, industries, SMEs, NGOs, local authorities, etc.

Table 5: PLATOON LinkedIn Profile

LINKEDIN		
	LinkedIn Profile: PLATOON.eu	PLATOON profile is intended as a mirror of the main updates on the PLATOON website. The most relevant contents and news of PLATOON will be posted on this profile in order to reach a wider audience.

Figure 12: PLATOON LinkedIn Homepage (admin view)

The screenshot shows the LinkedIn admin interface for the PLATOON.eu company page. At the top, there's a navigation bar with 'Start', 'Ihr Netzwerk', 'Jobs', 'Nachrichten', 'Mitteilungen', 'Sie', 'Apps', and 'Anzeige aufgeben'. Below that, the page title is 'PLATOON.eu' with 'Administratorsicht' and 'Mitgliederansicht' buttons. The main content area features a cover photo of a wind farm, a profile picture, and the company name 'PLATOON.eu' with the tagline 'Digital platform and analytic tools for energy'. The bio reads: 'H2020 Project on Digital PLAtform and analytical TOOLS for eNergy'. There are buttons for '+ Folgen' and 'Website besuchen'. On the left, there's an 'Analysen' section showing 'Aktivitäten der letzten 30 Tage' with 43 individual visitors (53% increase), 11 new followers (83% increase), 764 impressions, and 10 clicks on the adapted button. The main feed shows a post by Michael Fribus from 23.3.2020. On the right, there's a 'Kontakte als Follower einladen' section with a list of contacts to be invited, including 薛冰晨, Moritz Hartmann, and Maximilian Nadicksbernd.

⁶ Cf. <https://www.linkedin.com/company/platoon-h2020/>

Figure 13: PLATOON LinkedIn Homepage (members' view)

Figure 14: PLATOON LinkedIn Posts

4.4.3 Project-specific YouTube Account

Table 6: PLATOON YouTube Account

YOUTUBE		
	<p>Account:</p> <p>PLATOON H2020 Project</p>	<p>Use for webinar uploads, and project related videos (e.g. interviews of the consortium partners, the accelerated start-ups/ SMEs and other related stakeholders).</p>

The project specific YouTube account⁷ is specifically designed for the PLATOON project, has been set up. Via this account, project related videos, including the videos of the planned webinars will be uploaded and further communicated. The links of the videos will be appropriately edited, when the channel will have more than 100 subscribers according to the regulations of YouTube. YT will be used to share audio-visual contents that will be shared on other media and platforms, including project related webinars showcasing important project developments. The partners will be asked to communicate the relevant milestones of the project, as well as their participation in project events on their social media profiles.

Figure 15: PLATOON YouTube Channel

4.5 Newsletters

An electronic newsletter will be distributed twice a year to the target audience. It will include updates on achievements and milestones. All electronic newsletters will be available and featured at the website in the press section. Additionally, specific mailing campaigns will be planned for a distribution of these newsletters through the network of contacts of the different partners participating in the project. This is especially important to address the

⁷ Cf. <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCWK6cuUikW53Ap26QggXTvA>

D9.1 – Dissemination and Communication Strategy

industrial audience, energy and data science stakeholders, policy makers as well as the generic audience. The newsletters will provide subscribers with a concise summary of all the latest PLATOON-related news since the last issue. Apart from reports about the project's progress and announcements about forthcoming events, etc., the newsletter will also contain news about important developments in the various fields related to PLATOON's activities, including contributions from all partners and all work packages. TIB as Lead of WP9 will update the consortium in a timely fashion and engage the consortium partners to share updates and content which will be included in the newsletters. Screenshots of the newsletters and related information will be shared in the yearly versions of D9.3. The appropriate GDPR issues and checks are considered and will be detailed in D9.2 and D9.3.

4.6 Dissemination Campaigns

Integrated communication campaigns will be designed in WP9 and launched by the PLATOON Consortium both complementing and being complemented by the project's dissemination activities and utilizing a variety of instruments and relations to communicate the project's success stories, audio-visual material and comprehensive information packages that will make the project results, along with the overall framework within which it is implemented and funded more understandable to a broader audience. The PLATOON communication campaign instruments will include, at minimum 1) the project's website, 2) social media, news portals, e-magazines, blogs and web TV channels, 3) press releases, newsletters, videos in popular media channels with diverse audience, 4) participation and presentation of the project and its results in stakeholder's workshops. Appropriate material (stories, documents, etc.), accompanied by audio-visually enhanced portraits and testimonials will target non-specialist general public, while media relations will be established through social media in order to engage journalists and bloggers to the project's social media releases (TW, LI, YT).

Project Website

The project website⁸ will regularly provide information regarding the project and its expected results, news, events' schedule, training materials, publications etc. The website is made using a modern Content Management System (CMS) – WordPress - and is operational on several media: desktop, laptop, tablet, smart phone. It will be continuously updated, in order to be relevant and attractive for all stakeholder groups and key actors. It serves as a dissemination and communication tool. As such, focus will be given in featuring blog posts and other communication content without project specific jargons like "deliverable", "work package" when necessary. In order to increase the visibility of the project web-promotion activities will be carried out such as social media campaigns or links at other websites. Special attention will be given to Search Engine Optimization⁹ (SEO) in order to increase the

⁸ Cf. <http://platoon-project.eu/>

⁹ Cf. <https://support.google.com/webmasters/answer/7451184?hl=en>

D9.1 – Dissemination and Communication Strategy

quality and quantity of website traffic by increasing the visibility of the website to users of web search engines. The website will be showcased in detail in D9.2. The website includes the appropriate section on GDPR, Ethics and privacy (more information on Data Privacy and Legal Notice can be accessed in Chapter 8.3), showcasing how personal data will be processed during the project. It includes the cookie declaration; detailing how cookies and tracking software are installed in the information Website for the Platoon European project, enable the Website to operate in an optimal way. Further updates will be listed in D9.3.

4.7 Industrial Dissemination

Some of the main target audiences of the Communication and dissemination strategy of PLATOON are related to the different industrial companies operating in the energy sector.

European companies need to explore innovative strategies searching for differentiation and niche competitive advantages, in order to beat low-cost competitors. The energy markets will increase significantly in the coming years, but at the same time customers will foster fierce competition to provide cost-competitive high added value solutions all along the energy value chains. One of the technologies that European industry is envisaging as a main source of relevant competitive advantages is the digitalization of the energy assets and infrastructures, in order to extract value out of the use and analysis of the data collected.

As the International Energy Agency (IEA) has stated¹⁰ “Digital data and analytics can reduce power system costs in at least four ways: by reducing O&M costs; improving power plant and network efficiency; reducing unplanned outages and downtime; and extending the operational lifetime of assets. The IEA estimates that the overall savings from these digitally enabled measures could be in the order of USD 80 billion per year over 2016-40, or about 5% of total annual power generation costs based on the enhanced global deployment of available digital technologies to all power plants and network infrastructure.”

Within this context, the results of PLATOON are expected to have a relevant impact on the competitiveness of companies at all levels of the European energy sector. That is the reason why a specific task (9.3) in WP 9 is devoted to Industrial dissemination. The activities planned in this Task 9.3 are addressed specifically to the following target segments of the energy value chains:

- **Developers and/or owners of energy assets:** utilities (TSOs, DSOs, retailers), renewable energy power plant operators (wind and solar, mainly), ESCOs. These companies are presently the owners of the assets that should produce (in some cases are already producing) data to be shared and analysed by the different stakeholders involved. Their main interest is to extend the life of their assets and increase the profitability by reducing operation and maintenance costs. For all these

¹⁰ Cf. Digitalization & Energy. International Energy Agency, IEA, 2017

D9.1 – Dissemination and Communication Strategy

reasons, they are one of the key targets to be addressed by PLATOON, in order to facilitate them the use of the monitoring and analysis tools to be developed and to encourage them to share the data collected, by ensuring the compliance of these systems with “data sovereignty” principles.

- **O&M service providers:** These companies provide operation and maintenance services of the energy assets (electricity grids, wind farms, solar power plants, and energy consumption facilities among others) under contract with the facility owners. These companies could improve the quality of these services and even extend their portfolio if they were able to access data from the assets they must operate and maintain. In most of the cases, these companies lack the skills and tools to use and analyse these data. Moreover, access to data is often a barrier as the asset owners do not make this information available to third parties.
- **Wind turbine Original Equipment Manufacturers (OEMs, Tier 1):** Once the commissioning of a wind farm is finished and the guarantee period starts, the wind farm owner and the OEM sign a contract that allows the OEM to collect, use and manage the data obtained from the wind turbines. Most of the OEMs have started to implement Condition Monitoring Systems and are involved in new developments, but with little or no data sharing and cooperation with other stakeholders from the value chain: customers, component suppliers, engineering firms. They also represent a key target segment to be addressed by PLATOON, in order to make them aware of the cutting-edge architectures and applications developed in the project and to encourage cooperation by guaranteeing data privacy and security.
- **Equipment and components manufacturers (Tier 2 and 3):** manufacturers of the equipment and components that are installed or assembled in the electricity transmission and distribution assets, in the renewable power plants and in consumption facilities are increasingly demanding access to real field data (status, performance, . . .) from their components during the asserts lifecycle. Their main objective is to improve products in terms of design and reliability of the components, to predict their remaining useful life and to reduce maintenance costs due to unscheduled downtime of their products. Most of them are open to collaborate with customers and/or end users in order to develop these solutions. They also are seeking the support and collaboration from ICT companies in order to implement technologies where they do not have expertise: sensors, Big Data, data analytics.
- **ICT (Information and Communication Technologies) companies:** these companies are developers of products and solutions based on digital technologies: sensors, communications, Big Data, data analytics applications (algorithms, machine learning, AI). Most of them are start-ups and SMEs interested in having easy access to big amounts of data produced in operational energy assets, so that they can manage and use those data in order to develop applications and knowledge to be offered to companies at the different levels of the energy value chain.

D9.1 – Dissemination and Communication Strategy

- **Research and development centres - testing facilities:** these entities play a relevant role in R&D related to sensing and monitoring systems (sensor development, communication protocols, standard architectures, advanced algorithms). Some of these entities own laboratories, testing facilities or even equipment prototypes, where new developments and applications can be tested and validated.

In order to reach relevant companies from all the above-mentioned target segments, PLATOON partners will carry out several dissemination activities all along the project development:

- **Participation in relevant exhibitions, events and conferences of the energy sector:** booths with posters and brochures, speeches and presentations in the official programs, participation in roundtables (see Table 7: Major Conferences, Events and Awareness Days of planned specific events).
- **Organization of workshops and conferences targeted to industrial European audiences.** These workshops will be focused on presenting the progress and deliverables of the project at different stages of development (one per year), but also on getting feedback and expressions of interest from industrial companies. PLATOON partners will be the main speakers and conductors of these types of events.
- **Periodic contacts and launch of collaboration initiatives with selected entities and stakeholders,** that can offer the framework and the support to boost and extend the impact of PLATOON dissemination activities. PLATOON partners have already established contact (as described in section 4.9) with BDVA (Big Data Value Association) and IDSA (International data Space Association), in order to interact and cooperate with members of these associations through “Task forces”, “Working groups” or “Energy communities”. PLATOON will also address Technological Platforms like ETIP-SNET and ETIP-Wind for this purpose.
- **Workshops and meetings with stakeholders at national and regional level.** The partners of PLATOON will also participate in meetings or events with companies and stakeholders at national or regional level to enlarge the potential audience for the project results. This kind of meeting has proven to be especially convenient to raise awareness about international projects among local SMEs.

4.7.1 Conferences, Fairs and Exhibitions

Table 4 here below lists about the Consortium’s plans throughout the project’s duration in terms of presenting the PLATOON project within the context of yearly, major related conferences, events and awareness days.

Table 7: Major Conferences, Events and Awareness Days

EVENT	DATES	PLACE	NO. OF ATTENDEES
Hannover Messe	1st ~ 5th of April, annually	Hannover (DE)	>6,500 exhibitors, >220,000 Visitors >1,400 Events
BDVA Summits & Conferences	All events and general assemblies scheduled by BDVA, incl. European Big Data Value Forum (EBDVF)	Brussels and EU level	>500 organisations >50 meetings and sessions
SEMANTICS (biggest EU industry Semantic Tech Event)	September, annually (2020 Amsterdam, 2021 Leipzig, 2022 Vienna)	EU	>450 attendees >60 sessions >30 exhibitors
ICT Day	December, annually	EU	>4800 attendees
International Fair of Technics and Technical Achievements	May, annually	Serbia	>600 exhibitors >22 000 Visitors
CIGRE Conference	June, annually	Serbia	>100 papers in 20 sessions >300 attendees
Intersolar/ESS	May-June, annually	Munich (DE)	>1,450 exhibitors >50,000 visitors
Wind Energy Hamburg	September, even years	Hamburg (DE)	>1,400 exhibitors >35,000 visitors
Wind Europe Electric City	April, odd years	Copenhagen (DK)	>300 exhibitors > 8,500 visitors
Enlit (European Utility Week + Powergen)	October-November, annually (Milan, 2020)	EU	>800 exhibitors >18,000 visitors

Papers will be submitted in the following scientific conferences in order to ensure the visibility of the project, as well as of its output and results, at the scientific community:

- ISWC / ESWC¹¹ (Both Industry track)

¹¹ Cf. <https://iswc2020.semanticweb.org/calls/call-for-industry-track-contributions/>,

D9.1 – Dissemination and Communication Strategy

- CARLA 2020¹²: Concepts in Action: Representation, Learning, and Application
- EEWK 2020¹³: 10th Enterprise Engineering Working Conference
- EKAW 2020¹⁴: The 22nd International Conference on Knowledge Engineering and Knowledge Management
- ERIS 2020¹⁵: The 1st ER International School on Conceptual Modelling
- FOIS 2020¹⁶: The 11th International Conference on Formal Ontology in Information Systems
- ICCS 2020¹⁷: 25th International Conference on Conceptual Structures
- ISAO 2020¹⁸: The 5th Interdisciplinary School on Applied Ontology
- JOWO 2020¹⁹: The 6th Joint Ontology Workshops
- Bolzano Summer of Knowledge for Semantic Technologies²⁰ (Summer School)

Before M1, TIB has ensured that PLATOON will be showcased in its booth at the Hannover Messe 2020²¹, in Hall 25, Stand G14²². Since the start of the project, Philippe Calvez, coordinator of PLATOON, presented the project at the BRIDGE²³ General Assembly, 11 February 2020 – 12 February 2020 in the premises of the European Commission in Brussels and at the event Navigating IoT Architectures and Standard Days 2020²⁴ in Brussels. The Consortium partner, Giroa Veolia attended the Berdeago Energy 2020 fair²⁵ from 31. January to 2. February 2020 in Durango, Spain and presented the PLATOON project. TIB, as lead of WP9, will be in close contact with the consortium partners and disseminate their attendance in related events, via blog posts on the project's website, by which will be further disseminated on TW and LI. All partners are advised to provide photos demonstrating their attendance and interaction with the public, which will be used in the project's communication channels, which respecting the protection of personal data and ensuring that the protection of personal rights²⁶ is appropriately considered and implemented. PLATOON will also be presented in the Sustainable Places²⁷ (SP2020) conference in October 2020. This will be extensively reported in D9.3.

<https://2020.eswc-conferences.org/call-for-papers-industry-track/>

¹² Cf. <http://resources.illc.uva.nl/LogicList/newsitem.php?id=9821>

¹³ Cf. <http://ciaonetwork.org/events/9th-enterprise-engineering-working-conference-ewk-2019>

¹⁴ Cf. <https://ekaw2020.inf.unibz.it/>

¹⁵ Cf. <https://eris2020.inf.unibz.it/>

¹⁶ Cf. <https://fois2020.inf.unibz.it/>

¹⁷ Cf. <https://www.iccs-meeting.org/iccs2020/>

¹⁸ Cf. <https://isao2020.inf.unibz.it/>

¹⁹ Cf. <https://www.iaoa.org/jowo/2020/>

²⁰ Cf. <https://summerofknowledge.inf.unibz.it/>

²¹ Cf. <https://www.hannovermesse.de/exhibitor/tib-leibniz-informationszentrum/H649847>

²² Cf. HANNOVER MESSE 2020 has been postponed to the week of 13 to 17 July. Deutsche Messe AG is thus responding to global developments related to the Coronavirus.

<https://www.hannovermesse.de/en/news/news-articles/hannover-messe-2020-postponed>

²³ Cf. <https://www.h2020-bridge.eu/>

²⁴ Cf. <https://www.ngiot.eu/event/navigating-iot-architectures-and-standards-days/>

²⁵ Cf. <http://www.clusterenergia.com/events/berdeago-energy020-feria-vasca-sostenibilidad-3>

²⁶ More information and the respective consent forms can be accessed in chapter 8.5 of this deliverable.

²⁷ Cf. <https://www.sustainableplaces.eu/>

Figure 16: TIB's Stand at Hannover Messe 2020

Figure 17: Information on postponed Hannover Messe 2020

Active participation in external events (conferences, workshops, symposia, fairs) is crucial to PLATOON's dissemination strategy as it allows direct contact with the research and relevant stakeholders communities with which the project wishes to engage. All partners will present PLATOON at external events with TIB providing coordination in terms of communication and dissemination, including communication material (brochures, posters, stickers etc.). Furthermore, PLATOON will promote the organization of workshops with top-level extra-EU institutions and research communities throughout the project's duration. The consortium partners will prepare and deliver papers, oral communications, presentations and posters at congresses, relevant events and selected international conferences. Other communication materials, such as leaflets, roll-up banners, standard presentations and videos can be used at industrial exhibitions and fairs.

In addition to such external events, the consortium partners of PLATOON will periodically host their own events which provide excellent dissemination opportunities for the project. All events will be listed in the "News & Events" section of the website and in the yearly version of D9.3, Dissemination and Communication Report. The aim is to foster collaboration with world-class institutions in the fields addressed by PLATOON, in order to exchange best-practices and strengthen PLATOON's output effectiveness and impact.

4.7.2 Communication and Dissemination of Open Calls

The project dissemination activities will be further supported by the open calls dissemination activities, which will have a communication plan as well, that includes: a preparation stage of activities, the launch of the open calls, the communication activities to attract applicants and a final press release and infographic illustrating the main results of the open call.

The preparation stage involves the development of a communication toolkit that will be sent to the partners so that they can also promote the open call. Also, the planning on the channels and the elaboration of the promotional pieces that are going to be used to communicate about the open call. It is important that the open call is also announced on the website of the project, with a link directing to the micro-site with details about it and with access to the application form that will be deployed by FundingBox.

There will also be a press release that will be sent to different media outlets, and partners will be asked to send it to their local media. Depending on the budget structure, some online paid ad campaigns could be used to target specific regions or groups in order to encourage and secure an important number of applications.

Once an open call is launched, regular posting is done on different social media channels, and promotion is done in the newsletter of the project as well. Partners should also post on their social media accounts and refer in their newsletter. For these, they will have a communication toolkit that will be provided by FundingBox.

The PLATOON consortium partners and particularly TIB and CEPV will also commit to several Face-to-face actions including: (1) Info days to inform potential FSTP recipients in prioritised verticals about an upcoming open call. (2) Info corners in world-class events at EU Level. We will attend EU world-class events, within the prioritised verticals, specifically addressed to disseminate an open call. (3). Webinars (virtual info sessions). We will organise 2 web-based info sessions to disseminate an open call. The agenda will include a brief presentation of the project, the open call requirements and a slot for proposers' time, where potential applicants can present their project ideas and look for potential partners. The sessions will be recorded for participants to be able to play the web-stream video recording at any time. Once an open call closes, a press release with an infographic informing the results of the number of applications will be published and sent to media outlets as well.

Table 8: Action Plan for Open Call Communication and Dissemination Activities

ACTION	DESCRIPTION
Communication Toolkit	<p>Create a communication toolkit to disseminate the open call that will be launched and send it to all PLATOON partners and possible supportive partners to do cross-dissemination. Find an example of the ICCar project here. The communication toolkit should include:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Platoon logos, corporate images and banners. 2. Platoon one-pager. 3. PR about the open call. 4. Social media posts examples for Twitter, LinkedIn and Facebook. 5. Email templates. <p>The content and call to action are focused on applying for the open call. All partners should distribute it within their networks trying to reach out to the media and other entities interested in cross-dissemination or in collaborating with the PLATOON project.</p>
Branded Content/Banners in specialized media	<p>Create a list with specialized media relevant for the PLATOON project target (newspapers, magazines, and blogs). Reach out to them by sending the PR and banners to see if they publish it for free -in case there is budget, negotiate a sponsored article. FundingBox will also share posts in the relevant communities on their Spaces Platform: (Funding Opportunities on FundingBox Community²⁸).</p>
Newsletter & Email Campaigns	<p>Information about the open call should be included in the Platoon newsletter and all partners should also include a section about the Open Call in their newsletters.</p> <p>The email template included in the communication toolkit with the call to action ‘Apply for PLATOON open call’ has to be sent to all partners’ databases.</p> <p>Partners should also send it to possible collaborators (influencers and other supportive entities) under cross-dissemination purposes.</p>
Search Engine Marketing	<p>If there is a budget assigned to promote the open call, an online marketing campaign will be launched, including AdWords (Search and Display), optimised by a marketing agency or freelancer.</p>
Social Media: LinkedIn Twitter Facebook	<p>Owned social media: work on a social media plan to disseminate the open call using Platoon social media accounts.</p> <p>Shared social media: All partners should share on their social media accounts posts about PLATOON open call that can be found in the</p>

²⁸ Cf. <https://spaces.fundingbox.com/c/fundingbox-community/collections/showcase>

D9.1 – Dissemination and Communication Strategy

	communication toolkit.
Offline Events	<p>Use the events to promote face-to-face PLATOON open calls by distributing flyers/one-pager.</p> <p>Gather leads and send them personalised follow up emails about PLATOON open calls.</p> <p>Info days: 6 info days, at national level, organized by core technical partners before both open calls.</p> <p>Info corners: attendance to main related events at the European level to inform about the open calls.</p>
Webinar & Q&A Session	We will organise at least one webinar or Q&A session about a PLATOON open call in the PLATOON community in order to support the application process for participants.
Reminders Emails	<p>Create a reminders strategy based on emails to be sent to the draft applicants with the call to action ‘Submit your application’:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. One month to deadline. 2. Two weeks to deadline. 3. One week to deadline. 4. Three days to deadline. 5. One day to deadline. 6. Submission day.
Phone Calls	Following the reminders email strategy, call the most relevant applicants by phone during the last week before the deadline pushing them to apply.
Surveys	Once the open call deadline has passed, send an email with a little survey about the open call to get feedback from applicants and improve the process.
PR after the open call	A press release will be launched after the open call listing the main results in terms of received applications and the next steps that will follow. There will also be an infographic illustrating these results.

Description of Cascade funding mechanism for open calls

The project involves Financial Support to Third Parties [FSTP] in the amount of 2 million euros. To this end, a robust process has been defined to choose up to 13 bottom-up projects that will develop building blocks for large scale pilots, new analytical tools for the toolbox (prototypes) and new services (MVPs- minimum viable product) within the PLATOON Technology Transfer Programme. There will be 2 open calls (starting at M13 and

D9.1 – Dissemination and Communication Strategy

M22) with preparatory tasks, and the full process per open call lasts 18 months, as detailed in Figure 8. Proposed open calls will overlap during this 9-month period (execution of the 1st open call and the preparation of the 2nd).

Phase 1: Bottom-up projects selection.

The type of bottom-up projects we look for are presented in detail in Section 4.3 (Figures 4.3-1) but, in general, consists of two types:

- *Technology Transfer Programme 1*: start-ups and SMEs developing building blocks for large scale pilots; new analytical tools for the toolbox.
- *Technology Transfer Programme 2*: start-ups and SMEs developing new services on top of existing technologies.

The activation of innovative bottom-up projects interested in submitting proposals will be done through entities already connected to partners ecosystems, through networks reaching out to SMEs from all around Europe, like the ‘Enterprise Europe Network’ and the ‘NCP network’ and by organising several info days, info corners in world-class events and webinars/live Q&A. Then, all proposals will go through an exhaustive sequential filtering process as illustrated and explained. After expert evaluation by independent experts, the ‘Selection Committee’ will be responsible for ranking the proposals and selecting the final ones, which will also be reviewed by the ‘Ethical Committee’. The proposals submission and selection procedure will be done through the ‘FundingBox Platform, a web-based system which allows managing the whole open call cycle according to EC standards, and will be managed by FBA in an efficient and rapid way that is transparent, free of conflicts of interest, confidential and non-discriminatory, in order to ensure equal treatment of all participants.

Phase 2: Bottom-up projects execution.

The bottom-up projects will then become part of the Technology Transfer Programme (T7.4), led by Tecnalia, which will consist of 2 stages.

- **Stage 1 - Inception.** The first step of the programme is to engage the talent and build up the best mentoring set-up. Selected teams will meet during a Welcome Event where they will be matched with a technical mentor. After that, the teams will work intensively over a 4 weeks period to define their Individual Mentoring Plan (IMP). This document establishes the KPIs and deliverables that will be considered when evaluating the bottom-up projects’ performance. As a result of this stage, a p of concept will be defined together with the mentors, including the roadmap to successfully execute the project (by the end of M2 of the programme).

Figure 18: Support Programme (Bottom-up projects execution)

- Stage 2 - Development.** The 1st programme will focus on developing building blocks for large scale pilots and new analytical tools for the toolbox. The outcome of the programme will be fully functional prototypes (TRL 5-6). The 2nd programme will focus on developing new services on top of existing technologies. The outcome will be Minimum Viable Products (MVPs) that are ready to be taken to commercial maturity by the participants in the programme or presented to additional early adopters interested in the technologies (TRL 7).

The Technology Transfer Programme is articulated as a totally customised service, where highly specialized technical mentors are specifically selected to fit the needs of bottom-up projects and guide them along the whole program. The Technical Mentors, who will be assigned to the teams, will be a Ph.Ds. or a Senior Researchers from Research & Technical Partners with a wide background in ICT, big data, analytics or energy sector, and with an overall vision of the challenges addressed in the programme. This concept, partially inspired by the Entrepreneur-in-Residence concept - a methodological approach used in the Venture Capital industry and by LEAN-Start-up Accelerators-, will be the central point of the mentorship program from the technical point of view. The Technical Mentors will support the teams in defining the PoC, as well as help to develop prototypes and MVPs. The Technical Mentor will act as a kind of ‘Advisory Board’ member for the selected teams complementing the capabilities of the team members and acting as the CTO for the project. The mentors will be coordinated since the beginning of program 2 during the ‘Train the Trainers’ session (WP7.4) to make sure that the allocated mentors work in a cooperative and integrated way with their team and other mentors. The mentors will also be part of the ‘Mentoring Committee’ which will evaluate the performance of the bottom-up project after each stage.

D9.1 – Dissemination and Communication Strategy

Figure 19: Bottom-up Projects

Finally, an exhaustive ‘Review Process’ will be implemented in order to do a proper follow-up of the bottom-up projects. There will be a ‘Review milestone’ at the end of both stages. The review will be carried out by the ‘Mentoring Committee’. All relevant information in terms of lessons learned gathered during the Bottom-up Projects execution, will be included in the ‘Bottom-up Projects lessons learned’ report.

TIB will actively support FBA with the launch of the open calls, their management and dissemination. The first open call will be launched in M13 and the second open call in M22. The open call will officially start with the announcement on the project Website and in the open call landing page. Once the open call is launched, and during the 2 months until the deadline, the following tasks will be carried out: (1) Contact points from technical partners will provide information, from a technical point of view, to the potential FSTP recipients. (2) Help desk. FBA will provide information and support to applicants regarding the formal aspects of the calls, incl. organizing a webinar; (3) Open call monitoring by FBA (4) Open call dissemination. TECN will define the actions to be done by all partners for the open calls dissemination. FBA will be in charge of coordinating the online dissemination of the open calls, based on ‘Growth Hacking Strategies’. Additionally, face-to-face actions per call incl. 6 info days (1 per each core partner + 1 FBA), 1 info corner in world-class events at EU Level, and 1 webinar per open call.

FundingBox will disseminate the results from the open calls and project results through a community portal that will be set up in M18. Also, other community building activities such as the ambassador’s programme and the supportive partners programme will serve indirectly as dissemination channels.

All communication activities pertaining to the open calls will be featured on the project’s website. The accelerated SMEs and start-ups will be featured in a dedicated website section. Relevant communication campaigns will be organised besides the launch of the open calls and will include interviews and other information of the accelerated companies, which will be disseminated by the project’s communication channels.

4.8 Scientific Dissemination

4.8.1 Publications

A major means to reach the target scientific audiences of PLATOON and spread the knowledge gained from research efforts is to publish results in peer-reviewed scientific journals. In order to keep track of the publications, a dedicated “PLATOON Publications Record” online document has already been created and is available to all partners. When a publication is achieved, the responsible partner should add a record with all the required corresponding details, i.e. type of publication, reference, official link, repository, link to repository and partner responsible. The filled-out document will act as a guide and will allow WP9 partners to evaluate and update the planned actions. In keeping with the EC’s guidance on open access publications, the involved PLATOON consortium partners will review each publication before it is published and agree on the most appropriate route (green/gold) to open access.

All consortium partners will strive to publish their results (according to the IPR protection strategy) in dedicated journals and magazines with JCR index in the energy sector and in the field of energy efficiency in buildings (IEEE Power Transactions, IEEE Transactions on Smart Grid, IEA Heat Pump Centre Newsletter, Energy and Buildings, or similar, as listed in section Scientific Conferences of this deliverable).

PLATOON will be publishing its substantive research writings in academic journals. All partners are encouraged to publish their work in academic journals. Authors of scientific publications should adhere to standard good academic practice, and particularly note the following:

- Mention EU support for the work,
- Notify the consortium of the publication,
- Take cognizance of the EC’s open access policy,
- Provide a digital copy to the consortium, to be made available on the website (if the publisher agrees with the open access self-archiving). If not, a link will be provided to an archive copy elsewhere, or a copy will be kept in storage in case self-archiving is not allowed.

Below, Table 6 provides a first overview of potential journals that partners could target with their articles. It should be noted that this list is currently incomplete and will be updated in the yearly versions of D9.3. As it is expected that publication of scientific papers will predominantly occur in the second half of the project, a more extended version of possible publication outlets will be provided in the iterations of D9.3, Dissemination and Communication Report.

In CA, which is prepared by ENGIE, it will be made sure that the other partners are updated when a beneficiary intends to disseminate the results of the project. We will consider the recommendation of EC that a beneficiary that intends to disseminate its results must give

D9.1 – Dissemination and Communication Strategy

advance notice to the other beneficiaries of — unless agreed otherwise — at least 45 days, together with sufficient information on the results it will disseminate.

Table 9: Journals

NAME OF JOURNAL	DEADLINES
IEEE	31 st December 2022
Journal of Energy Engineering	31 st December 2022
Energy and Buildings	31 st December 2022
Engineering Optimization	31 st December 2022
ISWC ²⁹	2 - 6 November 2020
ESWC ³⁰	31 May - 4 June 2020

4.8.2 Scientific Conferences

Apart from publications in journals, the work of PLATOON will be presented in conferences, which will be a key mechanism by which to engage and involve the research community in this project. A tentative list of such conferences/congresses is presented in the table below. More information can be found the section Scientific Conferences of this deliverable.

Table 10: Scientific Conferences

CONFERENCE	DATE	LOCATION
IDSA – Winter Days ³¹	End of 2020	TBD
Bridge	2021	TBD
BDVA Conference	2021	TBD
WindEurope ³²	27-29 April 2021	Copenhagen, Denmark

4.8.3 Scientific Workshops and Meetings

Similarly, as scientific conferences, the partners will participate in workshops to discuss the project in more detail with target audiences. Later in the project, workshops will be hosted by the PLATOON partners to engage potential users in the project.

²⁹ Cf. <https://iswc2020.semanticweb.org/>

³⁰ Cf. <https://2020.eswc-conferences.org/>

³¹ Cf. <https://www.internationaldataspaces.org/idsa-winterdays/>

³² Cf. <https://windeurope.org/ElectricCity2021/conference/>

D9.1 – Dissemination and Communication Strategy

TIB, as WPL, will support all partners with their communication and dissemination activities pertaining to PLATOON, and will provide related consulting, guidance and ensure the high-quality visibility of such actions by actively engaging all communication channels of the project. The following table indicates how WP9 will communicate and support the dissemination of the output of the other WPs of the project, and their specific objectives.

Table 11: Communication & Dissemination of the Work Packages

WP	COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION FOCUS
WP1	<p>The WP9 Lead will participate in the process of the definition of the main challenges of big data tools and architectures for optimized energy system management, that will be elicited as specific requirements for the PLATOON reference architecture and corresponding building blocks that will be further identified, developed/ integrated and deployed in further technical WPs. TIB will attend WP related telcos and activities supporting via a communication angle the dissemination of the output of this specific WP. This includes the definition of representative business cases and their subsequent demonstration in the LSP activities as well as the specification of requirements from the different perspectives (data exchange, platform, business and legal/ethical).</p>
WP2	<p>The main objective of WP2 is the definition of the reference architecture for the PLATOON project and interfaces to external systems, focusing on the definition of the key enablers to guarantee interoperability in the energy domain in terms of standards, common data models and open API. WP9 will collaborate with the involved partners and regularly update the website of the project considering the produced output.</p>
WP3	<p>The objective of WP3 is to define an integrated data governance framework that ensures data security and respects data privacy and sovereignty, as a basis for secure data sharing (including the exchange of data and data services) to be carried out in PLATOON. The governance model and concepts promoted by the IDS will be adapted to fit the project's energy-specific data and stakeholders. WP9 will ensure that the results extended in a prototype for an energy data marketplace, compliant with IDS to not limit its potential, to which PLATOON platform users will automatically be given access will be appropriately communicated via the communication channels of the project, e.g. website, brochures and social media.</p>
WP4	<p>WP4 will develop the analytical toolbox component of the PLATOON platform formed by both generic big data tools and energy specific analytical tools for different applications. WP9 will participate and populate the respective website section, dedicated to the analytical toolbox. From a communication standpoint, the objective would be to understand to what extent distinct tools will be developed, and ideally communicate the tools in the respective website</p>

D9.1 – Dissemination and Communication Strategy

	<p>section, including information such as tool type, category, description, use case/pilot, contact person etc. Communication actions will aim to allocate a different logo per tool and produce a brochure dedicated to the toolbox.</p>
WP5	<p>This WP will work on software integration of the different modules developed in WP2, WP3 and WP4 in a form of PLATOON platform that will facilitate the development of new data-driven services and ensure that security, privacy, and access-control policies are enforced in all the components of the distributed system. This will be reflected at the project's website at the dedicated platform section. WP9 will produce a brochure dedicated to the PLATOON platform which will be updated during the project aiming to reflect the latest status.</p>
WP6	<p>The main objective of WP6 is to set up, deploy and operate large-scale pilots (LSP) that make use of digital platforms, data governance schemes and data analytic toolboxes, to develop prototype applications on top of the platforms, and validate the platforms in both reduced, controlled environments and in real-life use cases. WP9 has foreseen the respective website section dedicated to the pilots, where relevant information for each pilot will be provided. Each pilot lead and participants will be regularly contacted by TIB, so that the website will reflect the latest status of each pilot. A pilot specific brochure and poster will be prepared and used for project related communication activities.</p>
WP7	<p>WP7 focuses on the implementation of the two Technology Transfer Programmes [TTP], accompanying the bottom-up projects selected with a full range of services during the two 9-months-long TTPs and building a live community around the PLATOON project. TIB will work closely with FBA in these activities, including the dissemination of the open calls, and will conduct communication campaigns based on the activities implemented within the context of this WP, e.g. dedicated website section with information as per the incubated SMEs and start-ups, interviews with the incubated SMEs and start-ups and related webinars (e.g. for the launch of the open calls), focusing on lessons learned and engaging actively the community of supportive partners and ambassadors, by promoting the prototypes and MVPs developed.</p>
WP8	<p>WP8 will set the foundation for effective deployment and exploitation of the PLATOON cyber-secure platform that allows for large-scale multi-party exchange and the necessary analytical toolboxes to make the existing energy system more efficient and its piloted services. WP9 will communicate the lessons learned as per the business opportunities for the PLATOON platform and services, the developed business models to enable projects commercial partners to take the PLATOON solutions forward. Moreover, communication action will focus on the definition of how policy and regulation can promote the new digital platform and analytical tools concepts and the promotion of the project's exploitable results. By communicating this business value, WP9 will actively support the exploring of associated market opportunities and the development of exploitation plans for sustainability and large-scale uptake beyond project lifetime from a communication and dissemination standpoint.</p>

D9.1 – Dissemination and Communication Strategy

WP10	The main goal of this WP is to provide a smooth organization and coordination of the project activities and to ensure a high quality of results to achieve a major impact. WP9 will contribute and support WP10 as required.
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The goal of WP9 is to organize and execute measures in order to disseminate and communicate the project and the results it will deliver with strict alignment to the project IPR principles. Thus, WP9 will facilitate sharing of knowledge with external, targeted audiences, as well as towards other units of the consortium partners, get feedback from those audiences, and engage them with the project through targeted dissemination activities e.g. presenting at academic and industrial conferences, holding workshops and meetings with developers and engineers, etc. Moreover, WP9 will promote the visibility of the project and raise awareness about the topics it addresses through effective communication and outreach activities, e.g. publications, the maintenance of the project website, the distribution of printed and electronic material, publication of press releases, etc.

In order to achieve the envisioned impact, WP9 will conduct WP-specific telcos with representatives from all the partners and attend telco of the other WPs. Via this close collaboration, TIB's objective is to identify the appropriate timing and opportunities for communication activities, e.g. organisation of webinars focusing on technical, business and other energy related aspects. Furthermore, TIB will aim to derive the input required for the scientific communication of the project's output, ensuring that all communication channels, e.g. website. Brochures, posters etc. will reflect the latest status of the project.

All WPs will be supported by and interact with the general dissemination activities, including the mapping of stakeholders and parallel activities. All activities will be supported by the website, the social media accounts, and other project communication tools and materials. The table below indicates dissemination and communication activities in relation to milestones, showcasing how the focus of the communication and dissemination will be adapted per milestone throughout the project.

Table 12: Communication of the Milestones

MILESTON E NO.	MILESTONE NAME	DUE DATE (MONTH)	DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES
MS1	Challenges and requirements, Dissemination strategy, Data Management plan.	M6	Established dissemination and communication strategy, Coordination of monthly communication telcos at the level of the consortium, Set up and active use of all communication channels leading to active engagement of stakeholders.

D9.1 – Dissemination and Communication Strategy

MS2	Reference Architecture, Data governance requirements, Analytical toolbox design, LSP validation plan, 1st open call announcement, Impact assessment.	M12	Participation in the technical calls and collaboration with the technical partners in order to prepare a brochure showcasing the toolbox, update the website section regarding the toolbox, implement a webinar showcasing the toolbox and circulate a press release focusing on the technical development of the tools.
MS3	Initial data governance framework, 1st round of cascade funding.	M18	Reflect the latest status of the tools on the project's website, Disseminate the open calls in close collaboration with FBA across all communication channels related to the PLATOON project, consortium and beyond, including related social media campaigns, Host a webinar on the open calls and technology transfer programme Publish timely the related press release pertaining to the open calls and tech transfer programme.
MS4	Data governance, Sec/privacy Analytical toolboxes, LSP validation plan, updated 2nd open call announcement, Exploitation plan and business models.	M24	Ongoing update of the project's website with related news and events Update of all communication material to reflect the project's status, Dissemination of the 2nd open call Implementation of webinars related, including related social media campaigns, Publish press release to announce the 2nd open call to technical and business aspects of the project.
MS5	Reference Architecture update, Reference implementation, 2nd round of cascade funding.	M27	Update of the architecture section of the website, Update of the architecture brochure Webinars on the updated reference architecture and the 2nd round of cascade funding, Press release on the latest technical development.
MS6	Data governance	M30	Update of the website, comm

D9.1 – Dissemination and Communication Strategy

	framework update, First results of LSP		channels and materials to reflect the latest project status, Implementation of webinars to showcase the latest status of the project, Publish press release showcasing the first results of LSP.
MS7	Analytical toolboxes update, LSP final validation Technology Transfer evaluation, Interoperability standards Exploitation for Large-Scale uptake beyond project lifetime.	M36	Finalisation of project related comm materials (e.g. brochures, posters etc.) and update of online media to reflect the latest status of the project, Final major project event organised Final webinars implemented highlighting all project angles, output, impact and lessons learned.

4.9 Partnerships and Synergies

PLATOON will implement a comprehensive programme of joint events (symposia, workshops, public presentations) either directly managed by the project, or co-organised and with other relevant international/national initiatives. Over the forthcoming 12 months, TIB and CEPV will identify themes for events, possible co-organisers and suitable venues and will plan fully at least one joint-event in that period, to take place in the first half of 2020. Contacts are already established with the many research communities and associations, e.g. the Big Data Value Association³³ (BDVA), International Data Spaces Association³⁴ (IDSA).

International event co-operations

PLATOON is promoting the organization of workshops with top-level extra-EU institutions and research communities throughout its duration. The aim is to foster collaboration with world-class institutions in the fields addressed by PLATOON, in order to exchange best-practices and strengthen PLATOON's output effectiveness.

Project workshops

To involve stakeholders more actively in discussions, theory and methodology developments and applications, the PLATOON Consortium will organise a series of 3 workshops in different countries. All workshop and event proceedings will be made available on the project's website.

³³ Cf. <http://www.bdva.eu/>

³⁴ Cf. <https://www.internationaldataspaces.org/>

D9.1 – Dissemination and Communication Strategy

Events in which the PLATOON Consortium will participate

The PLATOON project will be presented at conferences, symposia, meetings, fairs. It is worth mentioning the energy domain related events and fairs, such as the EU Sustainable Week, workshops organised by KIC Innoenergy or CleanTech, as an example of reference events to attend. Moreover, brokerage meetings in the energy domain will be proactively attended.

Advisory Board

PLATOON will actively engage energy sector stakeholders (consumers and providers) and disseminate the output of the project across the stakeholders spectrum as identified in Section 5., Stakeholders. PLATOON's Advisory board will be established and consist of 5 partners that will provide impartial advice. This external and independent Stakeholder Advisory Board (SAB), consisting of related high-level stakeholders, will provide unique insights by highlighting areas where the PLATOON solution can add value. TIB will organise regular meetings with the SAB members during the project. Furthermore, the SAB members will support the PLATOON project, by increasing its visibility and status via dissemination activities and by indicating potential customers. The SAB will be featured prominently on the website, in the respective section. Furthermore, relevant communication actions will be organised with the board members, e.g. interviews and social media campaigns.

Network of associated partners

The network of associated partners will be established by the consortium partners. From a WP9 standpoint, the associated partners will be featured on the project's website and related communication activities will be implemented (e.g. interviews and social media campaign). Moreover, all collaborations implemented with the associated partners will be reflected in the news section of the website.

Ambassadors

It is foreseen that the PLATOON project will collaborate with the 6 ambassadors who will increase further the visibility and stakeholder engagement during the project. WP9 will work closely with the ambassadors, who will be featured in the respective website section. Interviews and social media campaigns will be implemented focusing on the ambassadors. Furthermore, the ambassadors will be provided the required input and guidance by WP9, in order to ensure that their actions will be fully and appropriately aligned with the scope and objectives of the PLATOON project.

Mentors

The mentoring committee will be featured on the website and the respective communication actions e.g. interviews and social media campaign, will be implemented. At

D9.1 – Dissemination and Communication Strategy

the same time, the mentors will be supported by WP9 to ensure that the envisioned communication impact is achieved, and their contribution is appropriately reflected on the project’s website.

5. Stakeholders

5.1 Stakeholder Groups

The PLATOON Consortium consists of 20 partners with different profiles: one wind plant operator (ENGIE), one DSO (SAM), the city of Rome as a municipality (ROM), two ESCOs (GIR, again ENGIE), two energy end users (PI, PDM), eleven technology providers (TECN, UBO, IAIS, ENG, VUB, IMP, TIB, IND, SIS, CS, UDGA) and three market enablers (MI, FBA, CEPV).

Stakeholder Mapping

Stakeholder mapping is an essential and basic step complementing the communication activities of the PLATOON project. In the process we identify the individuals and groups that are likely to affect or be affected by our proposed actions and results. Then, we group them based on their impact and interest factors on the actions as well as the impact the actions may have on them. By assessing this information, the consortium gets a clearer vision on how the interests of those stakeholders should be addressed both in the project communication and dissemination plan as well as relevant activities. The following project stakeholders are identified and categorized in connection to the PLATOON project based on the figure below:

Figure 20: Stakeholder Communication

- Group 1 ‘Keep informed and 'satisfied’’: relevant national policy makers, EU Energy Union

D9.1 – Dissemination and Communication Strategy

- Group 2 'Manage closely': EU Commission Services, PLATOON Partners
- Group 3 'Monitor': business and energy service provider community, the general public, media
- Group 4 'Keep informed and involved': expert panel, scientific community, workshop participants, decision and policymakers.

The Consortium will make use of its vast support network, some examples of which are listed in the table below. This list is to be expanded through the stakeholder analysis process implemented in D9.1 and refined during the project. Selected stakeholders are already supporting the implementation of PLATOON.

Table 13: Stakeholder Groups

STAKEHOLDER GROUP	BRIEF DESCRIPTION	WHY IS PLATOON INTERESTING TO THEM?	HOW TO ADDRESS THEM?
PLATOON Consortium partners	All 20 partners directly involved in the PLATOON project. Wide range of institutions: enterprises, research institutes, public institutions, etc.	PLATOON is of crucial importance to all Consortium partners as it aligns fully with their organisational goals and strategic direction in the domains of digitalisation and the energy sector in particular	Social Media: YouTube, Twitter, LinkedIn (YT, TW, LI), Printed Media, Newsletters, Webinars, Workshops, Trainings, Website, Video Tutorials, Podcasts
Energy generation companies/ Energy Service Companies (ESCOs)/ Renewable Energy (REN) Companies	Commercial enterprises that focus on generating electricity, heat, hot water etc., as well as energy services to businesses and private households. Also focus on companies that specialize in renewable energy, green electricity trading and e-mobility.	Should be prepared for emerging big data in the energy sector; links to partners with expertise in Big Data. Operation and maintenance of REN power plants, as well as electricity grids can be improved (f.e. easier to foresee upcoming maintenance work, optimised grids thus longer lifespan of those). The project aims to increase the RE share within the energy sector. By doing so, new REN businesses could be created which is especially good for start-ups and companies	Fairs/ Exhibitions, Webinars, Workshops, Trainings, Newsletters, Social Media (TW, LI, YT), Website, Specific Communication Campaigns, Printed Media, Video Tutorials, Podcasts

D9.1 – Dissemination and Communication Strategy

		with innovative business models.	
TSOs/ DSOs	Transmission System Operators and Distribution System Operators that operate and maintain electricity and gas grids; those who provide whole local areas or municipalities with energy.	Should be prepared for emerging big data in the energy sector; links to partners with expertise in Big Data.	Fairs/ Exhibitions, Webinars, Workshops, Trainings, Newsletters, Social Media (TW, LI, YT), Website, Specific Communication Campaigns, Printed Media, Video Tutorials, Podcasts
Small and medium enterprises (SMEs)	Small and medium-sized companies that focus on a business that is very closely linked to the energy sector; f.e. energy-heavy industries such as the automotive sector, mechanical engineering sector, pharma sector, construction sector etc. Especially those companies that have innovative and future-oriented business models.	Should be prepared for emerging big data in the energy sector; links to partners with expertise in Big Data. The project aims to increase the REN share within the energy sector. By doing so, new REN businesses could be created, and this could be a chance for industries that could provide these with services, goods, know-how etc.	Fairs/ Exhibitions, Social Media (TW, LI, YT), Website, Specific Communication Campaigns, Printed Media, Webinars, Trainings, Workshops, Video Tutorials, Podcasts
Energy End Users/ Building owners	Businesses and private households that consume energy. Also, those households/ businesses in	Easier access to cheaper, more digitized and sustainable energy. A more decentralized energy	Fairs/ Exhibitions, Social Media (TW, LI, YT), Printed Media, Specific Communication Campaigns

D9.1 – Dissemination and Communication Strategy

	<p>focus, that possess a REN plant in their homes, or those who want to buy eco power.</p>	<p>system can be created that lowers costs for the energy users and interconnects households with each other (esp. via smart grids); energy security could be improved.</p> <p>Increased energy efficiency for buildings, offices etc. leading to significant cost savings.</p>	
EU	<p>Political instances of the EC that represent the interests of the European Union.</p>	<p>Increasing the REN share to reach the ambitious 2050 emissions goals.</p> <p>Help to create an inter-European energy grid that is better interconnected and much less dependent on fossil fuels (thus energy supply security on EU-level could be increased).</p>	<p>Newsletters, Social Media (TW, LI, YT), Specific Communication Campaigns</p>
Municipalities	<p>Cities, settlements or communes that are responsible for certain local/ national/European areas.</p>	<p>Energy efficiency, optimised energy asset management and social welfare are key priorities of all municipalities and policy makers.</p> <p>Moreover, PLATOON addresses other topics such as smart cities, which are highly relevant</p>	<p>Social Media (YT, LI, TW), Website, Journals, Press releases, Newsletter and Project Communication Material</p>

D9.1 – Dissemination and Communication Strategy

Universities and Research centres	Public and private research and educational institutions that focus on providing people with constantly improving and up-to-date knowledge.	The project results/ milestone results are an important input that could enable universities and research centres to exchange knowledge, technology, data etc. and provide other stakeholders with valuable information (f.e. other scientific institutes, companies, etc.).	Social Media (YT, LI, TW), Website, Journals, Specific Communication Campaigns, Printed media
General public	All private persons that are generally interested in energy, REN, data science, ecology etc.	<p>The general public, i.e. private persons, could be potentially interested in up-to-date energy related topics such as REN, climate change, energy supply security, smart grids, and smart cities a.o.</p> <p>PLATOON addresses the interests of the general public due to the broad range of the topics that the project deals with. Thus, it can engage citizens who are not directly linked to the energy sector to engage themselves into energy topics and become proactive.</p>	Fairs, Social Media (esp. TW, YT), General Communication Campaigns, Printed Media
Funding agencies	Commercial enterprises and public institutions (f.e. Economic development companies) that are	Funding agencies focus on state-of-the-art developments in their sector.	Fairs/ Exhibitions, Social Media (YT, LI, TW), Website, Specific Communication Campaigns, Webinars, Workshops, Trainings

D9.1 – Dissemination and Communication Strategy

	providing start-ups, SMEs and projects on EU level with know-how and financial resources.	PLATOON being an innovative project funded by the EC, will make sure to communicate its output to funding agencies in relevant domains.	
Technological Platforms & Professional Associations and Initiatives	Public platforms that focus on technology-based topics such as Big Data, data Science etc. Example: Leibniz-Gemeinschaft.	PLATOON implements the digitalisation of the energy sector. Its use cases and pilots are highly relevant to related platforms and associations in terms of technology transfer, state of the art and lessons learned which can spur further synergies.	Journals, Social Media (YT, LI, TW), Website, Newsletters, Webinars, Workshops, Trainings

The dissemination and exploitation strategy of the project focuses on the target groups listed below. Hereby, each of the 20 PLATOON consortium partners represents the needs and interests of different stakeholders:

- *Market and Industry Stakeholders.* These stakeholders are involved in the development and commercialization of the PLATOON solution and constitute the key beneficiary groups of the PLATOON project results. CS and SIS represent the interests of SMEs while ENGIE acts as a large energy company and as an influential player on the energy market.
- *Technology Providers,* such as heat pumps manufacturers, thermal system controls developers, Building Management Systems hardware providers and control developers, ESCOs, utilities, variable renewable energy generators, etc. At this, UDGA stands for standardisation experts and is therefore representing technology providers, whereas ENG and IND both are ICT companies.
- *Public and Private Promoters in the renewable and energy sectors.* They are positioned at the heart of the project's dissemination and exploitation activities and constitute the main participants and receivers of the PLATOON demo sites awareness, engagement and training activities. Their involvement in the project's activities is considered of high importance since they will be the final end-users of the project's developments. TIB as leader of WP9 is responsible for all dissemination and exploitation activities and engaging actively with public promoters.
- *Electricity Market Actors,* such as grid operators (DSO, TSO), BRP's, aggregators, etc. The Advisory Board is formed by a good combination of each of these stakeholder's representatives: ENGIE and SAM represent the energy companies, while GIR stands for energy service providers.
- *Building Owners / Energy Consumers.* They are directly involved in the project's activities, being the actual consumers of energy in buildings. They will be involved in the PLATOON demo sites activities in a twofold manner, focusing, both, on (i) their awareness raising and engagement in interaction activities that will allow for the definition of accurate behavioural/ comfort profiles and (ii) the mitigation of concerns about privacy violation and personal data collection. PI is seen as an institution that focuses strongest on the needs of energy end users.
- *Technological Platforms and Professional Associations and Initiatives.* These actors target the advancement in integration of ICT and non-ICT systems for energy efficiency in buildings and districts, along with the promotion of sustainable

D9.1 – Dissemination and Communication Strategy

strategies, smart cities and smart grids (mainly focusing on peak load management and demand response). Within this context, PLATOON will establish clear synergies with (among others) the European and international associations, standardization and certification bodies related with the technologies developed in the project like smart grids task force, smart grids, among others. IAIS, IMP, TECN and TIB all are research institutes, while PDM, UBO and VUB are universities.

- *Public Institutions and Policy Agencies.* The EU Commission and national contact points; local authorities & national/regional public bodies (like municipalities) are key players as policy makers; national and regional energy agencies; companies and research centres. There are two instances that cater to the interests of policy makers, namely ROM and CEPV, while MI is regarded as a legal expert.
- *Scientific Community.* This target group corresponds to research and academic organisations, scientific journals, committees, internet fora, and other working groups in research fields related to the PLATOON work. Also as for technological platforms IAIS, IMP, TECN and TIB as research institutes as well as PDM, UBO and VUB as universities represent the interests of the scientific community altogether.
- *General public.* Citizens, consumers and their associations; specialized organizations and groups of interest. All of the consortium partners address the interests of the general public to a certain extent.
- *Funding agencies.* FBA represents cascade funding management experts.

5.1.1 Stakeholders on National Level

The interaction with stakeholders at the national level will aim at inspiring and coordinating with the development of plans and actions and framework conditions at national level.

Table 14: Stakeholder Groups on National Level

STAKEHOLDERS	RATIONALE FOR INVOLVEMENT	DISSEMINATION SOURCES
Policy makers	Interacting with the development of national framework conditions.	Policy briefs Official websites
Central governments, incl. governmental institutions related to energy and spatial planning	Interacting with the development of National framework conditions.	Newsletters Magazines

D9.1 – Dissemination and Communication Strategy

Associations of municipalities	Multiplier and interest organisation for municipal development and priorities.	<p>Events: Energy days, conferences, tours, seminars, workshops</p> <p>Scientific journals</p> <p>Press media (newspapers, online news etc.)</p> <p>Focussed dissemination actions of PLATOON on local level</p>
Public Organisations related to Spatial Planning	<p>Enhancing administrator`s knowledge and capabilities in sustainable energy planning.</p> <p>Ensuring the integration of the energy aspect in the spatial planning processes and legislation.</p>	
Energy Service Companies – ESCOs	Access to financing is a key to implementing major measures.	
Research community & Academia	Coordination with scientific research at national scale (urban planning, spatial planning, energy planning etc.)	
Energy Technologies Industry (national scale)	Enhancing understanding on expected impacts of sustainable energy planning. Coordination of actions.	
Energy Supplier Associations (national scale)	Typically, many measures and initiatives at local level are related to the energy suppliers, including fuel conversion projects, smart energy projects etc.	
Business Associations, Networks and Chambers (manufacturers, consultants, etc.) - multipliers and interest organisations for businesses a.o.	Enhancing the understanding of the need for integrated sustainable energy planning. Provision of supporters to the RLL concept and its replication.	
NGOs on environment and sustainable development (often also represented by local representatives)	NGOs can help to focus attention on the social and environmental externalities of activities.	

D9.1 – Dissemination and Communication Strategy

Networks on urban planning and sustainable development	Enhancing the understanding of the need for integrated sustainable energy planning. Networks can facilitate the dissemination of the project's output.	
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5.1.2 Stakeholders on European Level

Special emphasis will be given to dissemination within a European dimension considering that the project focus and the expected outcomes and results will be meaningful and significant at both European and international level. The dissemination at European level will aim at liaising with the development of EU policies and strategies and facilitate Europe-wide dissemination, replication and exchange of results and know-how with parallel initiatives. Within and beyond the project duration it is envisaged that there will be presentations in related congresses.

5.1.3 Stakeholders on International Level

PLATOON will identify and engage with stakeholders that share the same focus on the digitalisation of the energy sector at an international level, and engage actively with them, promoting the results of the projects at an international level. This will be accomplished via social media campaigns, the promotion of PLATOON's newsletter and by directly contacting such agencies and sending them the press kit of PLATOON, which will be available on the website.

5.2 Other Related Associations, Initiatives and Projects

This will involve collaboration with relevant projects and other initiatives at European, national and regional/local level. WP9 will regularly remind the consortium partners to propose related initiatives and projects with which synergies that can be established during the project. Some relevant associations, initiatives and projects at European level are listed here below.

Table 15: Other Related Projects

PROJECT	DESCRIPTION	SYNERGIES
BRIDGE ³⁵	Cooperation group of smart grids and energy storage H2020 projects	Participation in joint events, workshops and work groups. Joint communication campaigns.
Data Platforms projects in the BDV PPP portfolio (e.g. TRUSTS ³⁶) ICT13, DT-ICT-11	Project portfolio focusing on Data Sharing Spaces, enabling secure data sharing, Energy Data Platforms, other sectoral Data Platforms	Participation in joint events, workshops and conferences, effort to establish synergies (e.g. webinars) with other data platform projects.
BDVA ³⁷	Collaboration with projects of the BDV PPP portfolio	Participation in BDVA PPP events, workshops and conferences Effort will be made to establish an Energy Task Force. Major project activities (webinars, organisation of workshops) will be communicated to BDVA with the objective that they will be further promoted via the communication channels of the latter (website, Twitter).

6. Multi-channel Communication strategy

6.1 Online

Social Media

Social media is gaining increasing popularity and is therefore an important dissemination channel for the project. The PLATOON Consortium believes this is a good means of outreach to the public and the presence of the project on major social networking platforms has been established from the early stages of the project. The purpose of social media tools will be proactively promoting the project and its results permitting a two-way exchange of information.

PLATOON has considered the following social media channels:

- Twitter: We propose to use the hashtag “#platoonh2020”, “#platoonproject” and “#platoonenergy” in order to be able to follow the traffic around the project. Nevertheless, it is highly recommended that the consortium partners tag the project appropriately. In the Kick-off, the WP9 lead organised a workshop on the

³⁵ Cf. <https://www.h2020-bridge.eu/>

³⁶ Cf. <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/871481>

³⁷ Cf. <http://www.bdva.eu/>

D9.1 – Dissemination and Communication Strategy

appropriate use of social media within the content of a European project in general and PLATOON. At the same time, WP9 will ensure that all blog posts posted on the project's website will be uploaded and disseminated via the project's TW account as well.

- LinkedIn company page: each partner / company can add the LI company page in their own professional profile and distribute relevant information about the project by publishing relevant posts and articles and tagging the project. At the same time, WP9 will ensure that all blog posts published on the project's website will be uploaded and disseminated via the project's LI company page as well.
- The project website will be updated with blog posts regularly at a weekly basis, thus reflecting all project related activities. These activities will be further promoted via the project's social media, with the link pointing to the website, where e.g. the complete text for the blog post will be available to be read. The blog posts will be written by all consortium partners and curated by TIB.
- YouTube: The videos and webinars produced during the project will be further disseminated via the project's website and social media accounts.

Social media will update on new technical results, publications, research data and events that might be of interest for the energy and computer science community and the private sector. It will also help to share the demos experience, build understanding, facilitate adoption of project results and collect periodic feedback to focus on the innovation needs of the sector. Social media will raise awareness of the project, its results, its benefits, their use and applicability, as well as seek support of policy makers and public institutions. Finally, social media will raise interest of the general public on the project topic and its impact on everyday lives. Social networks will also be used to build up the project's community online. All project partners must contribute to the social media content.

6.1.1 Website

Figure 21: PLATOON Website Homepage

Figure 22: PLATOON Website News & Events on Homepage

Partners

[View more](#)

Figure 23: PLATOON Website Contact Section

Figure 24: PLATOON Website Consortium Section

Figure 25: PLATOON Website News & Events Section

The PLATOON website will be the main information showcase of the project. It is developed by ENGIE in close collaboration with TIB. The domain name of the website is <http://platoon-project.eu/>. A complete functional and operational website is foreseen for M4.

Website efficiency will be underpinned by the criteria of:

- Usability. Clear and accessible structure
- Content updating
- Accuracy in the content suitability
- Provision of relevant and current information to a wide audience.
- Serving as an information database of all the activities and public deliverables implemented by the project and its partners related to the PLATOON project.

All partners will be requested to deliver content for the website. The working language of the website is English. Nevertheless, effort will be made that major project updates, which will be communicated as Press Releases, will be translated by the partners in the languages of the Consortium and featured as well on the project website, in the “Press” section.

The website map has been designed to offer a complete overview of the project and an easy access to all its activities. Moreover, there will be a main “News & Events” section promoting the latest updates related to PLATOON calls, events or activities open to the public. The download areas will be available per section, giving the possibility of free downloads of all the public outputs carried out during the project’s life, including the brochures of the project, its media kit, public deliverables etc.

D9.1 – Dissemination and Communication Strategy

The website will also allow visitors to formalize their online subscriptions to PLATOON events and to register for the project's newsletter.

As of now (M3), the following structure is proposed and implemented for the project's website. Of course, this structure can further be updated and adjusted during the project in order to serve best the project's objectives.

Main menu tabs:

- Home
- About PLATOON
- News & Events
- Platform
- Community
- Pilots
- Resources
- Contact

The following subsections are proposed:

1) "About PLATOON" has the following subsections:

- 1- Overview
- 2- Scope and Objectives
- 3- Approach
- 4- Impact
- 5- Expected Results
- 6- Consortium Partners
- 7- FAQ
- 8- Press
- 9- Dissemination Materials
- 10- Stakeholders

2) "News and Events" has the following subsections:

- 1- News
- 2- Press Releases
- 3- Interviews

D9.1 – Dissemination and Communication Strategy

- 4- Open Calls
- 5- Webinars
- 6- Workshops and Conferences
- 3) “Platform” has the following subsections:
 - 1- Description,
 - 2- Energy Big Data Analytics Tools
- 4) “Pilots” has the following subsections:
 - 1- Overview, and then 1 tab per pilot:
 - 2- Predictive Maintenance of Wind Farms
 - 3- Electricity Balance and Predictive Maintenance
 - 4- Electricity Grid Stability, Connectivity and Life Extension
 - 5- Office Building: Operation Performance thanks to Physical Models and IA Algorithms
 - 6- Advanced Energy Management System and Spatial (multi-scale) Predictive Models in the Smart City
 - 7- Energy Efficiency and Predictive Maintenance in the Smart Tertiary Building Hub
 - 8- Energy Management of Microgrids
- 5) “Resources” has the subsections
 - 1- Publications,
 - 2- Deliverables,
 - 3- Material

The newsletter subscription, including the privacy policy and legal notice can be accessed directly on the home page. After the project’s conclusion the web site will be online for at least 2 more years, during which the materials and results of the project will be available for project participants and for the public.

6.1.2 Newsletter and Mailing List

The free, six-monthly newsletter will be broadcasted by electronic channels (email, social media) to the online subscribers and will further disseminate the progress and output of the project. The newsletter is planned for M6, M12, M18, M24, M30 and M36. It will essentially synthesise the project advancements and provide links to download the reports and relevant information elaborated in PLATOON. The newsletter will provide information in a synthetic form, which will be accessible in full version on the PLATOON webpage.

PLATOON will often disseminate its free of charge newsletter subscription. TIB and ENGIE have access to the emails of the subscribed stakeholders, via an installed plug in on the website. Complying with the privacy policy and legal notice, it will be further explored if a mail list will be hosted e.g. via the popular Mailjet platform³⁸, which is preferred based on the fact that it stores personal data in its secure data centres with Google Cloud Platform in Frankfurt (Germany) and Saint-Ghislain (Belgium).

Our goal over the next 12 months is to populate our mailing list. During the first two months, we will focus on gathering the details of individuals working at the PLATOON partner institutions. Nevertheless, this mailing list focuses more on participants from organisations and external institutions. The partner recipients of the newsletter will be encouraged to spread the PLATOON newsletter among their own networks and mailing list, including social media accounts, which are expected to gradually result in a substantial number of subscribers from outside the PLATOON consortium. TIB and ENGIE manage the PLATOON mailing list. All partners will contribute to its population (forwarding of newsletters, spreading the word, etc.).

6.1.3 E-Journal and Open Access Repository

WP9 will evaluate the need for creating a scientific e-journal covering the field of humanities research. It will further investigate the possibility of setting-up and managing a scientific repository service for open access pre-print storage of scientific papers. Over the forthcoming 12 months, we will investigate the community requirements and needs for an e-journal and repository in conjunction with the technical WPs.

6.2 Printed Promotional Material

6.2.1. Brochures

The production of brochures, posters and roll-ups in national languages will widen the public that will be reached by the communication activities, allowing other potentially interested stakeholders and the general public to be informed about the PLATOON project. We envisage having a brochure that will focus on specific elements of PLATOON (consortium, target audience, events, funding calls, etc.). The brochure will exist in electronic form to be forwarded via e-mail and downloaded on the website. Furthermore,

³⁸ Cf. <https://www.mailjet.com/>

D9.1 – Dissemination and Communication Strategy

there will be printed versions to be used for conferences and live events. While preparing the brochure, special attention will be given to an appealing and clear language and a friendly, light design which represents the idea of the project via nice pictures and key visuals.

Information shown in the brochure will be adapted to additional formats: posters and rollups. These elements will be printed and available for partners to be used in specific dissemination actions in events, or workshops promoting the PLATOON project (booths, corners, etc.).

At the same time, customised brochures will be prepared and updated during the project, focusing on specific project angles. For instance, dedicated brochures should reflect the project pilots separately, the developed platform and its components, the open calls etc. TIB will work closely with the technical partners and constantly update such material which can be downloaded from the project's website, e.g. in the press section and in the specific sections as well (e.g. platform section of the website).

Additional efforts will be made when the final PLATOON event approaches in terms of design of new specific promotional material for this individual event that will take place at the end of the project. Hence, the focus of this new material will be on the final outcomes and results of the project achieved along these 3 years. We envisage producing at least the following materials for the event:

- Customized event agenda layout
- New version of the PLATOON brochure
- Brochure adaptation to rollup format

These brochures along with a project poster will be the major printed materials to be used for dissemination purposes during conferences, workshops and other awareness events. The consortium partners will be offered the possibility to translate the brochure in their national languages. This will be used for the dissemination of the project outcomes and results at national level and beyond the project duration. In addition, an infographic showcasing the output of the project will be developed and promoted in an abstractive form that can be communicated widely through internet media easily.

As WP9 leader, TIB will be responsible for these productions. To communicate the project objectives and expected results, promotional brochures will be designed and made available to be distributed in relevant events and in digital version. The updated versions of the communication materials will be included in the yearly versions of D9.3, Dissemination and Communication Report.

Description of the first version of the brochure

To facilitate the explanation of PLATOON's purpose and its opportunities, the first version of the brochure has been prepared resuming the project objectives and scheme. The brochure contains four pages and can be folded like a little book. It includes all logos of the 20 PLATOON consortium partners, as well as a variation of the PLATOON logo on a violet-blue background. Below the PLATOON logo, the flag of the European Union has been placed with

D9.1 – Dissemination and Communication Strategy

a short text acknowledging the funding of this project by the EC and the corresponding GA number.

On the inside of the brochure, the PLATOON project is described in a few bullet points with keywords highlighted in bold. The brochure also includes information on the TW, LI, and YT page of PLATOON, as well as on the project's website. All links are placed right next to an individually designed "Smart City" image that gives the flyer its unique character.

Figure 26: Brochure (external side)

Figure 27: Brochure (internal side)

This brochure will be distributed in conferences, workshops and other events where consortium members will present and promote the project. Other similar materials will be elaborated to contribute to the communication of diverse PLATOON key messages, such as the results of the pilot projects.

PLATOON will provide a range of materials for non-academic audiences. Special efforts will be made to present complex ideas in an accessible and understandable manner. The consortium partners will be invited to translate the brochures in their national languages and redistribute via their organisations' networks.

Besides the brochures, TIB will support the preparation of flyers for project specific actions, e.g. dissemination of open calls, webinars, workshops etc. Similarly, as the brochures, the flyers will be distributed in digital or print form to all stakeholders.

6.2.2 Posters and Roll-ups

Within six months after the start of the project, each project partner must place at least one poster with information about the project (minimum size A3), including the financial support from the EC, at a location visible to the public, such as the entrance area of a

D9.1 – Dissemination and Communication Strategy

building. The poster must stay visible for the whole duration of the project. The partner (TIB) in charge of communication will create and distribute posters to all implementing partners. The posters will be regularly updated and customised to reflect the latest status of the project, including specific project angles.

Figure 28: PLATOON Poster Version 1

Figure 29: PLATOON Poster Version 2

6.2.3 Promotional Stickers

For dissemination purposes, stickers will be prepared and distributed within the consortium and beyond for dissemination purposes. The stickers will provide the following info serving the purpose to arouse interest for the project and direct to the project's website:

- the European Union's logo and the reference EU, acknowledging the received funding and GA number,
- the name of the project

D9.1 – Dissemination and Communication Strategy

- the project’s logo and website address, along with reference to its accounts on LI, TW and YT.
- Visuals highlight the project’s scope and objectives, focusing on the digitalisation of the energy sector.

Screenshots of the current versions of the stickers can be accessed here below. The stickers will further be adapted throughout the project’s duration, if necessary.

Figure 30: Sticker Version 1

Figure 31: Sticker Version 2

6.2.4 Other Promotional Merchandise Articles

TIB will ensure that an updated media kit will be available on the project’s website. Each partner is free to design and produce promotional items suitable for distribution to stakeholders during the local dissemination events (e.g. T-shirts for conferences etc.). Nevertheless, before such items are prepared and circulated, TIB, as the leader of WP9, has to be updated and review the proposed design and promotional actions. This is justified by the fact that TIB serves as communication consultant for the consortium and as WP9 lead at the same time. Hence, TIB has the obligation to ensure that this EU funded project is appropriately promoted, and the received funding is correctly acknowledged. Such

D9.1 – Dissemination and Communication Strategy

promotional items will be featured in the yearly versions of D9.3, Dissemination and Communication Report.

7. Evaluation and Monitoring of Dissemination and Communication Activities

The Dissemination and Communication Strategy (D9.1) ensures that all foreseen actions and methodologies in D9.1 are accompanied by the appropriate monitoring and evaluation plan and actions, operationalising all the methods of measuring success in detail. The official mid-term evaluation of the strategy can lead to an appropriate realignment for the second half of the project. Furthermore, the dissemination reporting is a task that will be carried out regularly and the corresponding report will be included in the annual and final reports. TIB will lead a monthly telco for WP9 with the objective to engage the consortium partners and collect their input for scheduled and implemented communication activities. Moreover, TIB has established an internal evaluation at the level of WP9, which will be implemented every six months. This evaluation will measure periodically the effectiveness of PLATOON's communication and evaluation activities and identify areas of improvement, as well as explore adaptations that might be required.

Each iteration of D9.3, Dissemination and Communication Report, will provide an assessment of the implementation of the previous plan, a comparison with the KPIs defined in the DoA, and provide targets for the forthcoming period.

Periodic evaluation is undertaken to guarantee that all our stakeholder communities are reached and provided with appropriate information. It also has an important role in shaping future iterations of D9.3 by providing feedback on what works and what needs refinement. All partners have a significant role to play in the implementation of the communication plan; their own dissemination activities will be detailed and evaluated at the level of the consortium in D9.3.

8. Obligations and Requirements for Communication Actions

8.1 Information on of EU Funding

All the communication guidelines of the EC will be respected and implemented throughout the project's duration (e.g. the Annotated Model Grant Agreement, article 38³⁹, Communicating EU research and innovation guidance for project participants⁴⁰, the EU Guide to Science Dissemination⁴¹, the social media guide for EU funded R&I projects⁴², the

³⁹ Cf. https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/amga/h2020-amga_en.pdf#page=277

⁴⁰ Cf. https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/gm/h2020-guide-comm_en.pdf

⁴¹ Cf. <https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLvpwIjZTs-Lhe0wu6uy8gr7JFfmv8EZuH>

⁴² Cf. https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/grants_manual/amga/soc-med-guide_en.pdf

D9.1 – Dissemination and Communication Strategy

IPR helpdesk brochure “Making the Most of Your H2020 Project. Boosting the impact of your project through effective communication, dissemination and exploitation”⁴³, the Graphics guide to the European emblem⁴⁴.

Visibility of EU Funding

In all communication tools, materials, written documents and activities, the reference to the funding by the European Union must and will be clearly indicated. The beneficiaries must — during the action and afterwards — ensure the visibility of EU funding for any communication activity related to the action (including in electronic form, via social media, etc.) and on any infrastructure, equipment or major result (including prototypes) funded by the grant, by: displaying the EU emblem and including the reference to EU funding set out in the GA.

Best practice: Where possible, beneficiaries should make this reference in the language of the communication activity or, for infrastructure, equipment or major results, the official language(s) of the country where they are located (using the text of the GA language version available on Funding & Tenders Portal Reference Documents).

The EU emblem and reference to EU funding must be displayed in a way that is easily visible for the public and with sufficient prominence (taking also into account the nature of the activity or object), e.g. as a sticker or poster for equipment and major results, a plaque or billboard for infrastructure.

As for the position, the fund mention must be placed on the left bottom of the page. In case the slogan is already placed there, it can be written under the name of the project or vertically on the right-hand side of the layout. The GA number must always be included, e.g. “This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 780495. Any dissemination of results here presented reflects only the consortium view. The Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.”

8.2 Disclaimer excluding Agency and Commission Responsibility

As defined in ARTICLE 38.1 — Communication activities by beneficiaries⁴⁵, it will be clearly stated and communicated that solely the consortium is responsible for communication content and project output. This will be also indicated by the addition of the following text, where appropriate, which will be customised depending on the context. For instance for reports and deliverables, the following text will be used; “*This report reflects the views only of the authors and does not represent the opinion of the European Commission, and the European Commission is not responsible or liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.*”; whereas on the website the following text is used on the

⁴³ Cf. https://www.iprhelpdesk.eu/sites/default/files/EU-IPR-Brochure-Boosting-Impact-C-D-E_0.pdf

⁴⁴ Cf. <http://publications.europa.eu/code/en/en-5000100.htm>

⁴⁵ Cf. https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/funding-tenders/opportunities/content/article-381-%E2%80%94-communication-activities-beneficiaries_en

D9.1 – Dissemination and Communication Strategy

home page: *“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 780495. Any dissemination of results here presented reflects only the consortium view. The Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.”*

8.3 Data Privacy and Legal Notice

The project is expected to generate datasets processed for experimentation, tests and validation. Thus, the project will abide by a strict policy of personal data minimization by avoiding collecting any unnecessary personal data in conformity with the General Data Protection Regulation. Where applicable, relevant datasets related to tests, validations and scientific publications will be stored by the corresponding WP leaders for 10 years and made available for verification and re-use through a CKAN open data server, which will be maintained as part of its research infrastructure. The project will address data protection issues comprehensively in D10.4 (Data management plan), D10.6 (Data management report), and D1.4 (Report on Legal and Ethics requirements). These deliverables will address in detail the process of data collection through online tools (e.g. newsletter) and the processing of personal data related to the communication activities of the project. At the same time the appropriate privacy and legal notice are included in the project’s website. Furthermore, the cookies policy is incorporated at the website, with the appropriate pop up.

8.4 Management of Intellectual Property and Open Access

Open access repositories of scientific data will be used and reported in D9.3. Moreover, the PEDR will appropriately ensure the Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) protection throughout all the three different stages of Project Phase, Follow-up Phase and Market Phase. Some of the components developed in PLATOON as well as any innovative aspects of this project are expected to generate Intellectual Property that must be protected and exploited in priority by members of the consortium, or alternatively by third parties through appropriate licensing. All partners will continuously contribute to the identification of project results that may qualify for Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) protection. The IPR policy will be described in the Consortium Agreement and will align with the EC Rules for participation and the guidelines provided by the IPR Help Desk⁴⁶. In D9.3 the access to types of data, data access, and data preservations will be reported. These data will be made available during the project until two years after the project conclusion (in order to enable the commercial activities for further steps in the products industrialization and commercialization, as well as business models implementation).

⁴⁶ Cf. www.iprhelpdesk.eu

8.5 Personal Photographs of People

The protection of personal rights is very important to the PLATOON consortium. Thus, all consortium members are required to ask for the consent of people they wish to take photographs of all the time at all events during the project. Two Consent Form templates are provided in the Annex. For project partners to use during workshops, events, academic conferences and other occasions.

9. Conclusion

D9.1 aimed to describe the dissemination and communication strategy for PLATOON, covering a vast range of actions to be implemented considering all the angles, objectives, and WPs of the project. Furthermore, D9.1 showcases how each communication channel will be actively and regularly used and aligned with the overall communication and dissemination strategy so that the envisioned impact is timely achieved. Regular monitoring and evaluation of the achieved communication and dissemination impact will be implemented in order to ensure that adjustments and adaptations will be implemented where necessary. Measures have also been taken to ensure the active involvement and engagement of the consortium partners and the wider PLATOON network (stakeholders, Advisory Board, mentors, associated partners etc.) in the dissemination of the communication activities and the provision of content which will be used for communication purposes (e.g. preparation of blog posts, interviews, collaboration for the implementation of webinars etc.).

Communication within PLATOON aims to complement the project's dissemination and exploitation activities, by providing universally understandable information to the general public about the project results and increasing the visibility of Horizon 2020 and the project's contribution to the digitalisation of the energy sector. To this end, the communication strategy of the project is built upon informing and demonstrating towards a wide range of audiences residing outside the core target groups of the project, the societal and economic benefits generated by PLATOON, by communicating tangible results and "human" success stories coming from the project validation activities (e.g. pertaining to the pilots, use cases and accelerated companies) and stimulating positive emotions through the demonstration of the social added value generated by the project. Through the exploitation of various mainstream communication channels and the attraction of additional stakeholder groups in the domains of energy, computer science, smart cities, entrepreneurship, climate and beyond, the consortium will attempt to increase awareness and enhance societal perception on how Research and Innovation can tackle emerging energy related challenges and positively impact the society, while increasing visibility and information flow on the vital role of H2020 and EU funded research in realizing and achieving ambitious EU-side societal, economic and sustainable growth goals in the domains related to the project.

10. Internal Review

10.1 Internal Review 1

Mark with X the corresponding column:

Y = yes	N = no	NA = not applicable
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Name of reviewer: Diana Järve

Organisation: FBA

Date: 19 March 2020

ELEMENT TO REVIEW	Y	N	NA	Comments	Author
FORMAT: Does the document ...?					
...include editors, deliverable name, version number, dissemination level, date, and status?	X				
... contain a license (in case of public deliverables)?			X		
... include the names of contributors and reviewers?		X		Contributor(s), Reviewer(s) to be added	Diana Järve
... contain a version table?	X				
... contain an updated table of contents?	X				
... contain a list of figures?		X		To be added	Diana Järve
... contain a list of tables?		X		To be added	Diana Järve
... contain a list of terms and abbreviations?	X				
... contain an Executive Summary?	X				
... contain a Conclusions section?	X				
... contain a List of References (Bibliography) in the appropriate format?	X			Contains footnotes	Diana Järve

D9.1 – Dissemination and Communication Strategy

ELEMENT TO REVIEW	Y	N	NA	Comments	Author
... use the fonts and sections defined in the official template?	X				
... use correct spelling and grammar?	X				
... conform to length guidelines (50 pages maximum (plus Executive Summary and annexes))		X			
... conform to guidelines regarding Annexes (inclusion of complementary information)			X		
... present consistency along the whole document in terms of English quality/style? (to avoid accidental usage of copy & paste text)	X				
About the content...					
Is the deliverable content correctly written?	X				
Is the overall style of the deliverable correctly organized and presented in a logical order?	X				
Is the Executive Summary self-contained, following the guidelines and does it include the main conclusions of the document?	X				
Is the body of the deliverable (technique, methodology results, discussion) well enough explained?	X				
Are the contents of the document treated with the required depth?	X				
Does the document need additional sections to be considered complete?		X			
Are there any sections in the document		X			

D9.1 – Dissemination and Communication Strategy

ELEMENT TO REVIEW	Y	N	NA	Comments	Author
that should be removed?					
Are all references in the document included in the references section?			X	Footnotes are used	Diana Järve
Have you noticed any text in the document not well referenced? (copy and paste of text/picture without including the reference in the reference list)		X			
TECHNICAL RESEARCH WPs (WP2-WP5)					
Is the deliverable sufficiently innovative?					
Does the document present technical soundness and its methods are correctly explained?					
What do you think is the strongest aspect of the deliverable?					
What do you think is the weakest aspect of the deliverable?					
Please perform a brief evaluation and/or validation of the results, if applicable.					
VALIDATION WP (WP6)					
Does the document present technical soundness and the validation methods are correctly explained?					
What do you think is the strongest aspect of the deliverable?					
What do you think is the weakest aspect of the deliverable?					
Please perform a brief evaluation and/or validation of the results, if applicable.					
DISSEMINATION AND EXPLOITATION WPs (WP8 & WP9)					

D9.1 – Dissemination and Communication Strategy

ELEMENT TO REVIEW	Y	N	NA	Comments	Author
Does the document present a consistent outreach and exploitation strategy?	X				
Are the methods and means correctly explained?	X				
What do you think is the strongest aspect of the deliverable?				Easy to read. Appropriate level of details.	Diana Järve
What do you think is the weakest aspect of the deliverable?				Figure names, table names not finalised yet. Footnotes should be revised, i.e. full details of receptive reference added.	Diana Järve
Please perform a brief evaluation and/or validation of the results, if applicable.			NA		

SUGGESTED IMPROVEMENTS

PAGE	SECTION	SUGGESTED IMPROVEMENT

CONCLUSION

Mark with X the corresponding line.

X	Document accepted; no changes required.
	Document accepted; changes required.
	Document not accepted; it must be reviewed after changes are implemented.

Please rank this document globally on a scale of 1-5.

(1-Poor; 2-Fair; 3-Average; 4-Good; 5-Excellent)

Using a half point scale.

Mark with X the corresponding grade.

D9.1 – Dissemination and Communication Strategy

Document grade	1	1.5	2	2.5	3	3.5	4	4.5	5
									X

10.2 Internal Review 2

Mark with X the corresponding column:

Y= yes	N= no	NA = not applicable
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Name of reviewer: Philippe Calvez

Organisation: ENGIE

Date: 30 March 2020

ELEMENT TO REVIEW	Y	N	NA	Comments	Author
FORMAT: Does the document ...?					
...include editors, deliverable name, version number, dissemination level, date, and status?	X				
... contain a license (in case of public deliverables)?			X		
... include the names of contributors and reviewers?	X				
... contain a version table?	X				
... contain an updated table of contents?	X				
... contain a list of figures?	X				
... contain a list of tables?	X				
... contain a list of terms and abbreviations?	X				
... contain an Executive Summary?	X				
... contain a Conclusions section?	X				

D9.1 – Dissemination and Communication Strategy

ELEMENT TO REVIEW	Y	N	NA	Comments	Author
... contain a List of References (Bibliography) in the appropriate format?		X			
... use the fonts and sections defined in the official template?	X				
... use correct spelling and grammar?	X				
... conform to length guidelines (50 pages maximum (plus Executive Summary and annexes)		X			
... conform to guidelines regarding Annexes (inclusion of complementary information)	X				
... present consistency along the whole document in terms of English quality/style? (to avoid accidental usage of copy & paste text)	X				
About the content...					
Is the deliverable content correctly written?	X				
Is the overall style of the deliverable correctly organized and presented in a logical order?	X				
Is the Executive Summary self-contained, following the guidelines and does it include the main conclusions of the document?	X				
Is the body of the deliverable (technique, methodology results, discussion) well enough explained?	X				
Are the contents of the document treated with the required depth?	X				
Does the document need additional	X				

D9.1 – Dissemination and Communication Strategy

ELEMENT TO REVIEW	Y	N	NA	Comments	Author
sections to be considered complete?					
Are there any sections in the document that should be removed?	X				
Are all references in the document included in the references section?	X				
Have you noticed any text in the document not well referenced? (copy and paste of text/picture without including the reference in the reference list)		X			
TECHNICAL RESEARCH WPs (WP2-WP5)					
Is the deliverable sufficiently innovative?			X		
Does the document present technical soundness and its methods are correctly explained?			X		
What do you think is the strongest aspect of the deliverable?			X		
What do you think is the weakest aspect of the deliverable?			X		
Please perform a brief evaluation and/or validation of the results, if applicable.			X		
VALIDATION WP (WP6)					
Does the document present technical soundness and the validation methods are correctly explained?			X		
What do you think is the strongest aspect of the deliverable?			X		
What do you think is the weakest aspect of the deliverable?			X		
Please perform a brief evaluation and/or validation of the results, if applicable.			X		

D9.1 – Dissemination and Communication Strategy

ELEMENT TO REVIEW	Y	N	NA	Comments	Author
DISSEMINATION AND EXPLOITATION WPs (WP8 & WP9)					
Does the document present a consistent outreach and exploitation strategy?	x				
Are the methods and means correctly explained?	x				
What do you think is the strongest aspect of the deliverable?				A global Strategy for dissemination and communication	
What do you think is the weakest aspect of the deliverable?			X		
Please perform a brief evaluation and/or validation of the results, if applicable.	X			Please perform a brief evaluation and/or validation of the results, if applicable. X The document exceeds the allowed number of pages (50) but clearly reflects a very structured and proven approach to highlighting PLATOON's work. The scope of the means mobilized to achieve these objectives are numerous and well interconnected.	

SUGGESTED IMPROVEMENTS

D9.1 – Dissemination and Communication Strategy

PAGE	SECTION	SUGGESTED IMPROVEMENT

CONCLUSION

Mark with X the corresponding line.

	Document accepted; no changes required.
	Document accepted; changes required.
	Document not accepted; it must be reviewed after changes are implemented.

Please rank this document globally on a scale of 1-5.

(1-Poor; 2-Fair; 3-Average; 4-Good; 5-Excellent)

Using a half point scale.

Mark with X the corresponding grade.

Document grade	1	1.5	2	2.5	3	3.5	4	4.5	5
									x

11. Annex

The two forms of consent are included in the Annex. Below is the consent form for photographic pictures and audio-visual recordings that can be accessed. This document is expected to be signed by all project participants and uploaded to the shared folder of WP9 as a scan. As decided, there is no need to maintain original versions of this document, so that scanned copies will be enough. Moreover, the same document can be used by the PLATOON consortium partners in their PLATOON related public activities, e.g. organisation of events, conferences, info days etc.

Consent Form I Photographic pictures and audio-visual recordings

Agreement between

Technische Informationsbibliothek (TIB), Welfengarten 1B, 30167 Hannover, Germany, represented by the director in the following "TIB" as a partner in the H2020 project "PLATOON" and

[please insert title, first name, last name, position, company]

hereinafter referred to as "the person photographed and/or recorded".

Subject Matter

Use of photographic pictures and/or audio-visual recordings in the H2020 project "PLATOON"

Purpose

Use of pictures

- Graphic editing and publication of photographs on the "PLATOON" project website for the visual presentation of the project team and the various contact persons
- Graphic editing and publication of photographs in relation to "PLATOON" project communication materials (print/digital) such as leaflets and posters as well as electronic newsletters
- Graphic editing and publication of photographs on Twitter and LinkedIn and YouTube to inform about project activities
- Provision of pictures to relevant stakeholders in the context of defined external project communication activities such as the distribution of press releases

Use of audio-visual recordings

- Editing and publication of audio-visual recordings on the "PLATOON" project

D9.1 – Dissemination and Communication Strategy

website

- Editing and publication of audio-visual recordings on Twitter, LinkedIn and YouTube to inform about project activities
- Provision of recordings to relevant stakeholders in the context of defined external project communication activities such as the distribution of press releases

Explanation

Dear everyone, GDPR is very clear about the fact that the employer is not allowed to oblige its employees to consent to the use of photographs of the individual. If someone does not want to sign the agreement, the project cannot publish their photographs. Please also be aware that the individual can rightfully object to the use of the data and in that case the use must be stopped immediately.

The person photographed and/or recorded declares his/her consent to the use of his/her photographs and/or audio-visual recordings produced explicitly for the purposes described above. It is not permitted to use the photographs for purposes other than those described or to place them on the market by making them available to third parties.

The person photographed and/or recorded has received the "Information Sheet" on the collection of personal data in the context of the use of photographs in accordance with Art. 13 GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation). This consent is voluntary. If it is not given, there will be no disadvantages. This consent can be revoked at any time with effect for the future.

We expressly point out that digital images can be accessed worldwide, for example on the project's website, and that further use by third parties cannot be ruled out.

Location, Date

Signature

Dear partner,

You are receiving this communication as TIB processes your personal information within the scope of the H2020 project "PLATOON" (grant agreement No 872592). This information sheet conveys important information about our privacy practices and your rights as it relates to your personal information. We encourage you to read this notice carefully and contact us if you have any questions.

INFORMATION SHEET ON THE PROCESSING OF PERSONAL DATA – PHOTOGRAPHIC PICTURES AND AUDIO-VISUAL RECORDINGS

TIB is required by law to protect your personal data. This notice explains how we process (e.g. collect, store, protect, delete) your personal data. We will process any personal data

about you in accordance with this notice and with applicable law.

1. WHO ARE WE?

The institution responsible for the processing of your personal data according to the data protection regulations is:

Technische Informationsbibliothek (TIB)

Welfengarten 1B

30167 Hannover

Represented by:

Prof. Dr. Sören Auer

Telephone: +49 511 7622531

E-mail: auer@tib.eu

A data protection officer has been appointed for our company:

Elke Brehm

Telephone: +49 511 762 8138

E-mail: Datenschutz@tib.eu

2. Purposes for the processing of personal data

Use of pictures

- Graphic editing and publication of photographs on the “PLATOON” project website for the visual presentation of the project team and the various contact persons
- Graphic editing and publication of photographs in relation to “PLATOON” project communication materials (print/digital) such as leaflets and posters as well as electronic newsletters
- Graphic editing and publication of photographs on Twitter and LinkedIn to inform about project activities
- Provision of pictures to relevant stakeholders in the context of defined external project communication activities such as the distribution of press releases

Use of audio-visual recordings

- Editing and publication of audio-visual recordings on the “PLATOON” project website

- Editing and publication of audio-visual recordings on Twitter, LinkedIn and YouTube to inform about project activities
- Provision of recordings to relevant stakeholders in the context of defined external project communication activities such as the distribution of press releases

3. LEGAL BASIS OF DATA PROCESSING

The processing of your personal data is in accordance with Art. 6, para. 1, letter A GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation) on the basis of your consent.

4. RECIPIENTS OF PERSONAL DATA

The recipients of personal data are:

- interested parties
- project partners
- funding agencies
- general public
- external auditors

5. TRANSMISSION TO A THIRD COUNTRY OR INTERNATIONAL ORGANIZATION

There is no transmission of your data to any third country (countries outside the European Economic Area, or EEA) on our end except to the countries where the headquarters and providers of Twitter, LinkedIn and YouTube are located. Otherwise your data will, in principle, be processed within the European Union.

Data on the internet can be accessed anywhere in the world, including in unsafe third countries where there is no adequate level of data protection. Therefore, we expressly point out that digital images, for example on our website, can be accessed worldwide and that further use by third parties cannot be ruled out.

6. DURATION OF STORAGE

Periods for retention result from the applicable H2020 provisions. In accordance with this, the data must be retained for up to five years after receipt of the project's final payment.

7. WHICH DATA PROTECTION RIGHTS DO I HAVE?

Each individual has the right to access in accordance with Art. 15 GDPR, the right to rectification in accordance with Art. 16 GDPR, the right to erasure (right to be forgotten) in accordance with Art. 17 GDPR, the right to restriction of processing in accordance with Art. 18 GDPR, the right to data portability in accordance with Art. 20 GDPR as well as the right to object in accordance with Art. 21 GDPR. Limitations in accordance with §§ 8-10 of the Data Protection Act of Lower Saxony apply to the right to access and the right to erasure. In addition, individuals have a right to lodge complaints with us. In this case,

please contact our data protection officer Ms. Elke Brehm as well as the competent data protection supervisory authority (Art. 77 GDPR in conjunction with § 19 BDSG). The competent supervisory authority is

Die Landesbeauftragte für den Datenschutz Niedersachsen

Barbara Thiel

Prinzenstraße 5

30159 Hannover

Telephone: +49 (0511) 120 45 00

E-Mail: poststelle@ldf.niedersachsen.de

8. AM I OBLIGED TO PROVIDE MY DATA?

Providing your personal data within the scope of internal and external communication activities relating to the H2020 project “PLATOON” (GA no. 872592), e.g. for the publication on the project website, in project promotional and publicity material or in the context of press work, is voluntary.

The following form of consent will be signed by each consortium partner and other entities (e.g. incubated SMEs and start-ups) that will be providing input (e.g. photos of conferences, where the PLATOON project is presented etc.) to TIB for posting and dissemination in the project’s communication channels (website, social media, webinars etc.).

Agreement between

Technische Informationsbibliothek (TIB), Welfengarten 1B, 30167 Hannover, Germany,

represented by the director

in the following “TIB”

as a partner in the H2020 project “PLATOON”

and

.....

represented by the director

D9.1 – Dissemination and Communication Strategy

in the following “project partner”

as a partner in the H2020 project “PLATOON”

hereinafter referred to as “the project partner”

Subject Matter

Production and use of photographic pictures and/or audio-visual recordings in the H2020 project “PLATOON”

Purpose

The project partner is a partner in the H2020 project “PLATOON”. Within the project, pictures and audio-visual recordings of employees of the PLATOON-project partners are to be produced and used for the visual presentation of the project team and contact persons on the project website and on Twitter, LinkedIn and YouTube, on project communication materials such as leaflets and posters as well as electronic newsletters and defined external project communication activities (e. g. to stakeholders) and press releases to inform about project activities.

The project partner guarantees, that the pictures and audio-visual recordings of employees of the project partners produced and offered to TIB for use for the purposes named above are produced during project events only with the knowledge of the person photographed and/or recorded or with the explicit consent of the photographed or recorded subject that the material may be used for the purposes named above.

Location, Date

Signature

The legal departments of TIB and ENGIE have agreed that scans of the aforementioned documents are enough. The consortium partners are welcome to maintain the original versions of the signed documents, if required by their legal departments.